

Revisiting
*The Crocodile Years: The Traditional Image of Science and
Physical Scientists' Participation in Weapons Research*

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Abstract

The primary motivation of most of the Manhattan Project scientists who built the first atomic bomb was fear: Werner Heisenberg's team of German scientists might build one first, and Nazi Germany would become unconquerable.

In November 1944, however, the United States and Great Britain learned by way of its secret ALSOS team that the German scientists were years behind the Manhattan Project and that a bomb could never be built in time to be used during World War II. Some six months later, on April 30, 1945, Hitler committed suicide. On May 8, 1945, the Allied Forces accepted Nazi Germany's unconditional surrender.

Why, then, did scientists in the United States continue to build and test an atomic bomb?

More than forty years ago, this author's doctoral research began in search of an answer to this question. The quest eventually evolved into an investigation of the relationship between science and weapons research and development (hereafter referred to as "R&D"), i.e., the relationship between scientists' views of science and their willingness to participate in scientific activity that ultimately results in weapons. The central research question became:

*Given the existence of a significant social demand for defense-related and weapons R&D,
why do some physical scientists participate in such research, while others do not?*

A theoretical model of the relationship between the social demand for defense-related and weapons research and development, traditional scientific values related to the worldview of classical physics, and differential participation by physical scientists in such research was developed and empirically examined. The model suggested that an antiquated "traditional image of science" exists, and that it may explain, in part, participation by physical scientists in defense-related or weapons research. The model was located within the sociologies of knowledge and science, and the dissertation included chapters that provided overviews of the literatures of these subdisciplines.

The two major hypotheses suggested by the model were: (1) that a constellation of values representing a "traditional image of science" obtains today among young physical scientists; and (2) that those who currently engage (or are willing to engage) in defense-related or weapons R&D are more likely to agree with the values implicit in the traditional image of science than those who do not (or would not) engage in such R&D.

The investigation concluded with an empirical examination of the model and hypotheses. Primary data, collected through 73 personal, in-depth interviews of a geographic sample of those who received doctorates in physics and related disciplines in 1983, were analyzed and interpreted.

The empirical findings supported both major hypotheses. Conclusions about the model and hypotheses were drawn from the findings, and suggestions for further research were provided.

Part One of this article is a ‘summary’ of a 235-page Ph.D. dissertation in sociology, forty years after its defense in 1985. At best, it introduces and contextualizes the investigation and highlights the most salient theoretical elements and empirical findings.¹

Part Two is an initial exploration of more recent published research on subjects related to the larger inquiry into scientists’ perceptions of science, scientific research and weapons of mass destruction. It is not intended to be a comprehensive survey of related research since the mid-1980s.

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Dedicated to the memories of
Robert Jay Lifton and Joseph Rotblat,
who lived lives of conscience and hope,
and worked to save humanity from itself.

Part One: Revisiting *The Crocodile Years*

Noncooperation in military matters should be an essential moral principle for all true scientists.
Albert Einstein²

Introduction

[The Mond Laboratory, which Ernest Rutherford had built for his “boys” – including the Russian physicist, Pyotr Kapitza – was dedicated in February, 1933.] The astonished participants in the opening ceremony beheld, carved on the façade, an extraordinary heraldic beast. It was a crocodile which had been chiseled in the stone at the special request of Kapitza . . . When Kapitza was asked what so utterly outlandish a creature was doing there, he replied: “Well, mine is the crocodile of science. The crocodile cannot turn its head. Like science, it must always go forward with all-devouring jaws.”

Robert Jungk³

Metaphors, like scientific models, are half-truths. To the extent that they help one better understand the objects or phenomena for which they are temporary surrogates, models and metaphors are useful and sometimes quite beautiful. Yet there is an inherent tendency in such abstractions to be misleading – and, on occasion, even dangerous – when they become permanent surrogates; that is, when they are confused with the reality they represent.

Pyotr Kapitza’s depiction of science as a crocodile with “all devouring jaws”⁴ is a humorous, satirical metaphor for what might be described as science’s historical blindness to, and apathy for, the social ramifications of its own progress. However, while it may be seen as behaving like a crocodile in one respect, science is certainly not a crocodile.

And yet the social institution of science is not unlike the metaphorical crocodile. In its pursuit of reason and order in the physical universe, science has created, for the most part, a world that is isomorphic with its own worldview. In so doing, science has often forgotten the metaphorical nature of its models and their assumptions; it has sometimes neglected to question seriously the epistemological ramifications of its own theoretical developments; and, consequentially, it has remained unaware of the inherent contradictions between its fundamental principles and the ways they become manifested in the social world.

Like Kapitza’s crocodile, science has pursued its goal of knowledge in such a tenacious fashion that its very momentum has come to legitimate both the value of its goal and its methods of pursuit. On balance, the social institution of science has forgotten that the knowledge it seeks and the models it employs are just metaphors. The evolutionary result of this phenomenon might be viewed as a theme not unfamiliar to scholars of Shakespeare: the fascinating drama within which appearance (image) is confused with reality.

Over the centuries, this confusion has contributed to the evolution of diverse – and often conflicting – social functions of science. One of the major manifestations of this phenomenon in the social world is the manner in which the scientific pursuit of knowledge has been married to defense-related and weapons research in Western culture.

Questions Arising Out of the Manhattan Project

The Faustian bargain is when you sell our soul to the devil in exchange for knowledge and power. And that of course, in a way, is what Oppenheimer

did, there's no doubt. He made this alliance with the United States Army, in the person of General Groves, who gave him undreamed of resources, huge armies of people, and as much money as he could possibly spend, in order to do physics on the grand scale – in order to create this marvelous weapon. And it was a Faustian bargain, if ever there was one. And of course we are still living with it ever since. When once you sell your soul to the devil, then there's no going back on it.
Freeman Dyson⁵

Why did these scientists continue to build the atomic bomb? Several caveats are worth noting here. First, discussions about the ethical implications of continuing the bomb's development were held by some of the scientists after V-D Day. Robert Wilson, a member of the Manhattan Project team at Los Alamos, remembers that at some point after V-E Day,

*I organized a small meeting at our building. I think the title was, "The Impact of the Gadget on Civilization." Oppie [Oppenheimer] tried to persuade me not to have it. I don't know quite why, but he certainly did try to dissuade me. On the other hand, I went ahead and did hold the meeting, and perhaps between thirty and fifty people came. Oppie came too, which always added a tone to any meeting. We did discuss whether we should go on or not, and in the context of what was happening in the world ... [it was suggested] that perhaps what we were doing was morally wrong.*⁶

Oppenheimer, however, argued for completion of the bomb because he said that he felt the world should know about it. Wilson recalls that everyone decided to continue in their efforts so that the existence of the bomb would not be a secret at a time when the United Nations was being organized.

On the other hand, May of 1945 was rather late in the game to be considering political and ethical questions. In her excellent history of the "Atomic Scientists" movement, Smith observes that speculation about the probability of alternate, political and military outcomes – as well as their implications – was uncommon:

*Only rarely did any of the scientists consider what would happen if Germany was defeated before the bomb was ready and it became not a defensive weapon against Japan, whose handful of excellent nuclear physicists could clearly not command the necessary industrial backing.*⁷

Second, it is important to acknowledge the constraints and imperatives of what Freeman Dyson has termed the "Faustian bargain", under which the military inevitably controlled the scientists' behavior to some extent. Third, it is paramount to understand one of the scientists' motivations at that point for continuing the bomb's development: it was believed by some that such a weapon would make the institution of war obsolete.⁸ Finally, the scientists involved were neither prescient nor did they have the benefit of historical hindsight with respect to their actions at the time.

However, what is most significant is that this new weapon of mass destruction did not need to be built (i.e., Germany was vanquished) – and if built, would be used against an unsuspecting people who were not racing to build such a weapon themselves. What is most important is that the scientists could have refused to continue the bomb's development. Except for the meeting he organized, Robert Wilson recalls that no one at Los Alamos thought of quitting the project after V-E Day. His reminiscences echo the image of Kapitza's crocodile of science, "which must always go forward with all devouring jaws":

Everything was coming together; everybody was working day and night. We were building up to the Trinity test, and it was very hard in the push to make that test to stop and think. I would like to think now that at the time of the German defeat,

*that I would have stopped, taken stock, thought it all over very carefully, and that I would have walked away from Los Alamos at that time. In terms of everything I believe in – before, and during, and after the war – I cannot understand why I did not make that act. On the other hand, it simply was not in the air. I do not know a single instance of anyone who had made that suggestion or who did leave. **Our life was directed to do one thing, and it was though we had been programmed to do that. And we, as automatons, were doing it.*** Robert Wilson⁹ [Emphasis is the author's.]

None of the scientists refused to continue to build the bomb after V-E Day.¹⁰ Instead, the new weapon was pursued to its completion. A major result of the scientists' pursuit of the bomb's successful development began with the deaths of hundreds of thousands of Japanese people in Hiroshima and Nagasaki on August 6, and 9, 1945. Moreover, the legacy of scientific research undertaken in the late 1930s and early 1940s cannot be separated from the Cold War that followed World War II and the arms race which today threatens the possible extinction of all life as we know it on Earth.

Several salient questions arise. First, why did these physical scientists look to weapons of mass destruction for hope along the road to peace? That is, why did they seek technological solutions to social problems? Why did they believe that the development of technology would somehow 'solve' the social problems of war and peace – and how would new weapons achieve such a task? While new technologies have historically influenced war strategies and foreign policies, the causes of war have never been identified as being located in the technologies themselves. The roots of the social institution of war, it is commonly acknowledged, are social (e.g., economic, political, ideological).

Second, why didn't these scientists refuse to finish the bomb after it was no longer needed to prevent Hitler from attaining such power for Nazi Germany? Or, perhaps more appropriately, what would have to have been different in order for the scientists to decide that the bomb should not be completed for ethical reasons alone?

Finally, the widespread concern (at the time of this dissertation) over the relationship between science, technology, and weapons R&D suggests fundamental differences between the 1940s and the 1980s in values and in perceptions of the social functions and responsibilities of science and its practitioners. These differences lead logically to the following questions. **Is it possible that these scientists shared similar values concerning the nature of science and its relationship to society? If so, which values?** And, most important to the purposes of this investigation, **is there a relationship between these values and physical scientists' participation in weapons research now (in the 1980s)?**

These questions informed the overall direction of the investigation. They invited an analysis of assumptions in the way science is practiced. In the most general sense, this investigation was an exploratory examination of the assumptions inherent in the manner in which science was practiced – and learned, in order to be practiced. Moreover, it was an examination of the relationship between values inherent in, and inculcated through, various socialization processes – through which the institution of science is maintained in society¹¹ – and participation by physical scientists in research that results in technologies of mass destruction. More generally, this study investigated the relationship between fundamental principles inherent in the classical scientific worldview and contemporary 'scientific' endeavors which contribute to weapons technologies and military 'solutions' to social conflict.

Assumptions and Premises

The thesis of this study assumed that the social demand for R&D of newer, more destructive weapons and systems of technological warfare has existed since the Manhattan Project and the end of World War II. This growing demand has had profound ramifications in many sectors of society. Of

particular importance was the inevitable influence such demand has had on society's expectations of physical scientists to engage in weapons R&D. This investigation is best understood in terms of the above assumption and the following three premises, which concern perceptions of science as well as the theoretical and empirical developments in science since Galileo and Newton:

- The practice of science has changed significantly during the past three hundred years. Scientific activity has been influenced as a whole by the larger social phenomena of industrialization, militarization, bureaucratization, professionalization, specialization and compartmentalization.
- Much of the way science is perceived by society and by many scientists has not kept pace with these changes in the character of scientific activity itself. Thus, this study suggests that **a traditional image of science** exists today in juxtaposition with the everyday reality of scientific activity. The vestigial elements of this traditional image of science remain relatively intact and can be found in the values of even newly trained physical scientists today. Adherence to these values appears to continue despite empirical evidence to the contrary in the everyday world of scientific activity.
- Certain theoretical and empirical developments have occurred during the 20th century that appear to challenge the integrity of the traditional image of science. These developments include, among other things, quantum mechanics and its epistemological implications. Despite such scientific developments, the traditional image of science still obtains in scientific society today.

The Traditional Image of Science

The traditional image of science includes “a definition of reality and a set of values which serve to guide and to justify the practice of a particular group”.¹² The ‘group’ in this study is comprised of physical scientists in Western scientific culture, specifically, those in the United States. The ‘definition of reality’ and the relevant values that comprise the traditional image of science may be described in the form of fundamental principles. That is, one way to describe the traditional image of science is through the development of a set of principles that reflect the definition of reality and values of the image.

Principles of the Traditional Image of Science

These principles derive from important historical moments and developments, including:

- the “Cartesian” delineation between mind and matter (in the 17th century);
- the “mechanistic world view” of Newton, which was based in part on the philosophical formulations of Descartes;¹³
- the “Fallacy of Misplaced Concreteness” – i.e., the assumption that the world was made of concrete bits of “matter” that were defined by what Whitehead calls “simple location”¹⁴;
- the establishment of scientific societies in Europe in the 17th century – specifically, The Royal Society in England – and the subsequent function of “value neutrality” in the relationship between the activities of those societies and the political and religious authorities of the time;¹⁵
- the tradition resulting from the scientific revolution (i.e., the revolution in natural philosophy) of the 17th century, in which knowledge and power are essential goals;
- the tradition of the German universities, “in which the cultivation of knowledge was considered as a good in itself, and also a contribution to the greatness of a nation”;¹⁶ and
- the early 18th century notion that progress was seen as “defining the character of human history ... and [the fact that] the apparently cumulative nature of scientific knowledge made the growth of science into a symbol of this optimistic faith.”¹⁷

Principles of the Traditional Image of Science

Objectivity:

- Objectivity is an important aspect of science and scientific research.

- Objectivity is possible and should be pursued.

Value-Neutrality:

- Scientists should not allow personal values to bias scientific research i.e., value-neutrality is an important quality of valid scientific research).
- Research free from the influence of personal biases is possible and should be pursued.

Subject/Object Distinction:

- A prerequisite for objectivity is the existence of a distinction between subject and object (i.e., between observer and observed; between scientist and the object(s) being studied) in scientific research.
- The existence of a distinction between subject and object is possible and should be pursued in scientific research.

Nonsocial Nature of Science:

- Scientific activity occurs – or should occur – outside social, political, and economic contexts (i.e., it occurs or should occur – within a social vacuum).

Scientific Pursuit of Truth:

- Through the use of scientific methods, scientists can discover the ‘mysteries’ and ‘secrets’ of nature and the physical world.
- ‘Truth’ can be discovered through the scientific pursuit of knowledge in the physical world.

Information as Knowledge:

- Scientific knowledge can be best characterized as an aggregation of information (as opposed to awareness).¹⁸
- Science “aims[s] at producing information either for its own sake or to enhance power over the surrounding world.”¹⁹

A Priori Beneficial Nature of Scientific Knowledge:

- The pursuit of scientific knowledge is ‘*a priori beneficial*’.²⁰
- The discovery of scientific ‘truth is ‘progress’ for humankind.

Characteristics and Importance of Scientific Methods:

- Scientific methods (which derive from the positivist, empiricist orientation of the physical and natural sciences) are primarily quantitative.
- Scientific methods are primarily model-oriented.
- Scientific methods are the only valid approach to knowledge.²¹
- Scientific methods are the most valid approach to knowledge.

Importance of the Physical World:

- The physical world is of primary importance in the pursuit of scientific knowledge. Other phenomena, i.e., those not involving the physical world, are of secondary importance.

Science as Material Progress:

- Increased material progress is the result of continued scientific economic and technological growth.²²

Legitimacy and Relevance of Technological Solutions to Social Problems:

- It is useful and appropriate to seek technological solutions to social problems.

A Theoretical Model of the Relationships Between the Social Demand for Weapons Research, the Traditional Image of Science, and Defense-Related and Weapons Research

Given the exploratory nature and scope of this study, and although there is some discussion about the logic of the influence of particular values upon specific types of social action, it is not the purpose of this research to develop a theory about how values and action are linked in the world of scientific activity today. That is, beyond a brief discussion of the manner in which objectivation, internalization, and externalization account for the transformation of social values into social action,

the specific dynamics and detailed components of such processes are not the focus of this study. As a preliminary inquiry, it is appropriate, instead, to survey the theoretical terrain in order to provide a broad-brush representation of the complex sociological relationships in question.

A caution about interpretation and significance is warranted. The model developed here should not be mistaken for the actual phenomena it is intended to represent. It is simply a heuristic device, designed to organize the empirical examination and inform further research in this area. In addition, the model should not be viewed as a causal interpretation of variables acting upon one another in total isolation from the larger socioecological niche to which it belongs. Rather, it is a visual illustration of informed (i.e., theoretical) speculation about complex, dialectical relationships among sociological phenomena related to physical scientists' participation in defense-related and weapons research. Finally, although there is some ordering of variables, primary emphasis should be placed on the potentially reciprocal nature of the relationship between social values and social action.

Variables in the Model

While the relationship between the traditional image of science and physical scientists' participation in defense-related and weapons research is the primary focus of this investigation, it only explains part of scientists' willingness to participate in such research. The model is comprised of five areas or sets of variables:

- the independent variable: significant social demand for defense/weapons R&D
- traditional scientific values (the TIS) and other cultural, political, and economic values
- intervening variables: those which provide a contextual frame of reference for the transformation of social values into social action
- the dependent variable: participation in defense/weapons R&D, and
- scientists' perceptions of, and relationships to, their work (included as part of one possible feedback loop, i.e., as indicative of the reciprocal nature of relationships in the model).

Figure 1.

A Theoretical model of the relationships between the social demand for weapons research, the Traditional Image of Science, intervening variables, and participation in weapons research

Hypotheses

The model suggests two major hypotheses (below) that articulate this study's fundamental concerns, i.e., (1) that those values which have been theoretically identified as comprising a "traditional image of science" obtain today in the value systems of young physical scientists, and (2) that there is a positive relationship between adherence to these values and participation in defense-related or weapons research:

1. The values of young physical scientists today include the values of the traditional image of science.
2. The greater the adherence to the values of the traditional image of science by young physical scientists, the greater the likelihood of their participation in defense-related or weapons research.

In addition, the model suggests a set of secondary hypotheses which posit relationships between other independent and intervening variables, on the one hand, and participation in military-related research. These hypotheses are stated below.

3. The greater the nationalism and patriotism, the greater the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research.
4. The greater the orientation toward violence and war as viable solutions to social problems, the greater the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research.
5. The greater the desire for upward mobility, the greater the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research.
6. The greater the degree of self-efficacy, the less the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research.
7. The greater the orientation toward the necessity or inevitability of the arms race, the greater the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research.
8. The greater the perception of the necessity or usefulness of defense or weapons research, the greater the probability of participation in defense-related or weapons research.
9. The greater the perception of the availability of employment opportunities, the less the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research.
10. The greater the perception that the job market was dominated by defense or weapons work, the greater the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research.

Of the eight secondary hypotheses proposed above, six posit positive relationships between the various independent or intervening variables and the dependent variable. Two hypotheses (i.e., #6 and #9) posit negative relationships between high self-efficacy and perception of an open job market, on the one hand, and participation in defense-related or weapons research.

Although the model includes variables involving the reference other orientation and the perception and relationship to work, hypotheses are not proposed concerning their relationships with the dependent variable because of the multidimensional (and subsequently ambiguous) nature of the variables and the qualitatively complex nature of the data to be gathered on these variables during the interviewing process.

Summary

The model presented here suggests one approach to an understanding of participation by physical scientists in defense-related or weapons research. It proposes that there is a dominant constellation of values held by those scientists who do engage in such research. The logic of the model is that such values manifest themselves in the conduct of physical scientists (i.e., in research) that is 'justifiable' by the values. For example, if physical scientists see their research as *a priori* beneficial or independent of its social consequences, it becomes much easier to either justify, or remain uncritical of, the ethical implications of the research.

Similarly, if research problems are addressed by questions that limit the analysis exclusively to mathematical, physical, or technological perspectives, it is highly unlikely that the resulting solutions, if

any, will involve variables unfamiliar to the physical sciences. That is, the model suggests that the existence of this constellation of values allows physical scientists to analyze, without benefit of social theory or sociological perspectives, the problems immediately before them; problems which are often merely symptoms of larger social problems. This process usually results in the development of technological solutions to isolated dimensions of complex problems that require transdisciplinary knowledge and collaboration. While it is understandable that physical scientists draw upon the skills which derive from their training, the resulting, compartmentalized 'solutions' often become new social problems themselves. At the same time, they divert attention from the original problems.

A case in point is the current 'scientific' debate about the Strategic Defense Initiative (or "Star Wars") proposal, put forth by the Reagan administration as a means of 'ending the arms race'. The debate focuses on whether or not the ideas are technically feasible, rather than questioning the logic of buying one more class of technologies to solve our arms race crisis with the Soviet Union. The causes of the arms race have little to do with the weapons themselves, although the momentum of the arms race is directly maintained and accelerated by the funding, research, and development of new weapons technologies. While the technological races for the latest generations of weapons and 'defensive' systems may, in all probability, increase the likelihood of war, all proposals like "Star Wars" have little or nothing to do with the causes of the problem, and everything to do with its symptoms.

It also is interesting to note that this fascination with the technological aspects of warfare has been transmitted successfully to the larger culture. Nonscientists responsible for arms control, for example, devote their efforts to technical analyses of weapons and delivery systems. As long as the focus of arms control remains limited to technical questions of the appropriate balance of weapons technologies for each side, the question of controlling the arms race (or, for that matter, the more fundamental question of disarmament) will go unasked, and the arms race will continue to escalate with every new technology that is introduced into the social equation of bilateral distrust and fear. In sum, it is axiomatic that the way a problem is stated will determine, to a great extent, the kind of solution that is finally employed.

An Empirical Examination of The Theoretical Model

Primary data, collected through 73 personal, in-depth interviews of a geographic sample²³ of those who received doctorates in physics, its subdisciplines, and related disciplines in 1983, were analyzed and interpreted.²⁴ The interviews were conducted in Arizona, California, Colorado, Nevada, and New Mexico from January – March of 1985. For the most part, interviews took place in respondents' homes or places of work. A few interviews took place in restaurants, but these were discouraged due to the background noise levels and the lack of privacy. All but one interview were tape-recorded,²⁵ and an interview guide was completed (by the interviewer) for each interview. The interviews ranged in duration from 55 minutes to two hours and 45 minutes; the average interview took 94 minutes to complete.

Interviewees worked in a variety of occupational settings, including: academia, private research institutes, federally-funded, scientific laboratories (e.g., the U. S. Geological Survey), private industry (including defense contractors as well as corporations with no relationship to the Department of Defense), defense-oriented 'think tanks' (e.g., like the Rand Corporation), national weapons laboratories (e.g., Lawrence Livermore Labs and the Los Alamos National Laboratories), and government-run nuclear testing facilities (like those near Yucca Flats, Nevada).

The sample was not generated in such a way as to preassign members into a control group (i.e., those who engaged in defense-related or weapons research) and an experimental group (i.e., those who did not). Pre-assignment would have required information from the sample that would have alerted its members to the examination's focus on issues concerning military-related research. This would have affected the final

make-up of the sample and biased their responses as well. Moreover, pre-assignment would have created an arbitrary representation of the proportion of each group in relation to the total population.

It is assumed, however, that the proportion of each group to the total represents, to some degree, the proportions found in the larger population. In order to determine respondents' participation in defense-related or weapons research, items measuring this variable were included in the interview guide.²⁶

Summary of the Findings

This section: (a) reports on demographic characteristics of the sample; and highlights (b) results of examinations of the hypotheses, (c) differences between the weapons scientists and non-weapons scientists in the sample, and (d) other findings related to comparisons of weapons and non-weapons scientists in the sample.

Demographic Characteristics

The sample is 97.3% male and has an average age of 31.6 years. The majority are married (61.6%), Caucasian (87.7%), and are citizens of the United States (91.8%). A plurality of the respondents grew up in the west (28.8%), attended colleges in the west as undergraduates (34.2%), and attended universities in the west as graduate students (41.4%). Two-thirds of the respondents received their doctorates in physics (all were in the physical sciences, mathematics, or engineering), and a great majority (96%) received their undergraduate degrees in the physical sciences, mathematics, or engineering. Only 2.8% have undergraduate degrees in the liberal arts or social sciences. Respondents' parents appear to be well-educated: 45.3% of respondents' mothers and 50.6% of their fathers have college or advanced degrees.

A plurality of the scientists are liberal or very liberal (49.3%) and see themselves as Democrats (42.5%). The largest group of respondents identified themselves as having no religious affiliation (30.1%). Of those with affiliations, Protestants comprise the largest percentage (35.6% of the total sample). A majority in the sample do not attend church at all (52.1%), and only 28.8% attend church once a month or more. Respondents have, on average, two siblings, and 56.2% were the first-born child in their families. Finally, personal gross incomes of respondents average between \$30-35,000; combined gross incomes average between \$40-45,000.

Salient demographic differences between scientists in the two groups involve political orientation and religiosity. Weapons scientists appear to be more conservative and identify with the Republican Party more than non-weapons scientists. The scientists in group one also are more likely to attend church regularly than are the scientists in group two.

Roughly half of all respondents (50.7%) in the sample see themselves as currently participating in research that has or may have military applications, and one-third of the respondents (32.9%) see themselves as currently participating in defense-related or weapons research.

However, the findings indicate that 53 of the 73 members of the sample either participate in defense-related or weapons research or are willing to do so in the future, while the remaining 20 respondents do not, or will not, engage in such research. Thus, nearly three-fourths (72.6%) of the scientists in the sample may be categorized in the first group (hereafter called “weapons scientists” or “group one” for the sake of simplicity), while slightly more than one-fourth (27.4%) of the scientists fall into the second group (hereafter called “non-weapons scientists” or “group two”). It should be noted that these proportions resemble almost exactly that percentage (72.4%) of total outlays for scientific research and development by the federal government corresponding to military and non-military-related research.

Major Hypotheses

Hypothesis #1 is strongly supported by the data. It states, “The values of young physical scientists today include the values of the traditional image of science.” A majority of the respondents agree or strongly agree to 20 of the 23 items that measure the traditional image of science values. Empirical support for this hypothesis is an extremely important finding.

Hypothesis #2 is strongly supported by the data. It states, “The greater the adherence to the values of the traditional image of science by young physical scientists, the greater the likelihood of their participation in defense-related or weapons research.” While only 5.0% (n = 1 out of 20) of the non-weapons scientists have scale scores indicating agreement or strong agreement with the traditional image of science scale, 22.6% (n = 12 out of 53) of the weapons scientists have similar scores. **In other words, more than four-and-a-half times as many scientists in group one agree with the TIS values than do scientists in group two.** While support for the first hypothesis is of great importance, **this is the most significant finding of the investigation; it has significant implications for this exploratory research and for the future of science as well.**

Secondary Hypotheses

The data also provide support for all but one (#5) of the remaining hypotheses. That is, a greater proportion of scientists in group one (than in group two) have higher scale scores vis-à-vis the following seven hypotheses below.

Three of the remaining seven hypotheses find strong support in the data:

- (#3) The greater the nationalism and patriotism, the greater the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research;
- (#7) The greater the orientation toward the necessity or inevitability of the arms race, the greater the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research; and
- (#8) The greater the perception of the necessity or usefulness of defense or weapons research, the greater the probability of participation in defense-related or weapons research.

The four remaining hypotheses find moderate support in the data:

- (#4) The greater the orientation toward violence and war as viable solutions to social problems, the greater the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research.
- (#6) The greater the degree of self-efficacy, the less the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research.
- (#9) The greater the perception of the availability of employment opportunities, the less the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research.
- (#10) The greater the perception that the job market was dominated by defense or weapons work, the greater the likelihood of participation in defense-related or weapons research.

Hypothesis #5 is the only one that is not supported by the data. It states, “The greater the desire for upward mobility, the greater the likelihood of participation in defense related or weapons research”.

The data analyses produced one additional finding, which is quite significant: **nationalistic and patriotic values and the traditional image of science values explain the most variance in physical scientists' participation in defense-related and weapons research.**

Findings Related to Comparisons of Weapons and Non-Weapons Scientists in the Sample

Traditional Image of Science Values

The distinctions between the two groups of scientists which are most important to this analysis involve adherence to the traditional image of science principles. Weapons scientists appear more likely to adhere to the traditional image of science values than non-weapons scientists. Of the 23 items measuring

the TIS values, a greater percentage of weapons scientists than non-weapons scientists agree or strongly agree with 17 items. The greatest difference between the groups involves the notion that science should occur outside social contexts. Two-thirds of the weapons scientists say they want science to be free of societal influences, as compared with only 15% of the non-weapons scientists.

Weapons scientists also agree more with the following principles (listed in order of magnitude of the difference) than do non-weapons scientists:

- that 'pure' science seeks information or knowledge for its own sake;
- that a delineation between subject and object is possible and should be pursued;
- that scientific research should be value-neutral;
- that a delineation between subject and object is ideally important in science; that the methods of science are primarily quantitative and model-oriented;
- that science is either the only valid – or the most valid – approach to knowledge;
- that scientific knowledge is information as opposed to awareness;
- that physical variables are of primary importance in the pursuit of scientific knowledge (or that other variables are of secondary importance);
- that value-neutrality and objectivity are possible and should be pursued;
- that the pursuit of science can discover 'truth(s)'; and
- that applied science seeks knowledge to control the physical world; and that the discovery of scientific 'truth(s)' is 'progress'.

On the other hand, non-weapons scientists are more likely to agree with six of the 23 TIS items. On five of the six items, agreement by both groups is quite high and variation between the groups is negligible. However, differential responses to TIS 23 indicate that more non-weapons scientists than weapons scientists believe that technological solutions are useful and appropriate for social problems.

Other Differences in Values and Perceptions. The findings indicate that weapons scientists in the sample are more nationalistic and patriotic than non-weapons scientists in the sample. Group responses to every item measuring nationalism and patriotism point to significant differences between the two groups of scientists. Weapons scientists also appear more likely than non-weapons scientists to: see war as a viable solution to social problems, believe in 'peace through strength', and say that killing other human beings during wartime is not against their moral principles. Furthermore, non-weapons scientists are less willing than weapons scientists to sanction the use of violence by the United States in its pursuit of democratic goals.

Findings concerning the desire for upward mobility suggest that scientists in both groups are interested in their status as scientists in the scientific community, but that non-weapons scientists are more interested in becoming successful and well-known as scientists, while weapons scientists are more interested in improving their financial situations. The findings also support the fact that weapons scientists are better funded than are non-weapons scientists.

Responses to items about empowerment and self-efficacy indicate that nearly all of the scientists believe in the importance of individual involvement, but that less than half actually get involved themselves in public or political issues. Moreover, the findings suggest that weapons scientists are less likely to get involved in public or political issues than are non-weapons scientists.

Scientists' perceptions of the arms race and disarmament include both similarities and differences. On balance, the majority of scientists in each group favor global disarmament, less military spending and more spending on domestic and social improvements, and the cessation of weapons production. Furthermore, the majority in each group believe that: weapons research is a major factor in the escalating arms

race, the arms race is everyone's responsibility, and scientists should try to influence the disarmament process. On the other hand, in every instance, weapons scientists favor disarmament less than do non-weapons scientists.

Weapons scientists appear to have a more positive orientation toward weapons research than non-weapons scientists. More scientists in group one than group two agree: that weapons research is necessary; that it would be necessary even without an arms race; and that the United States is spending either the right amount or too little on military-related research. Moreover, non-weapons scientists are more likely to agree that: nuclear weapons are not essential, nuclear war is inevitable, nuclear war is likely in the next 20 years, and a 'limited nuclear war' is unwinnable. Finally, a majority of weapons scientists say that a viable, space-based defense system like "Star Wars" is possible and should be pursued, whereas a majority of non-weapons scientists disagree. In fact, more than twice as many weapons scientists as non-weapons scientists say that such a defense system is possible. Similarly, more non-weapons scientists than weapons scientists perceive that escalation of the arms race into space is dangerous and should be stopped now before it is 'too late'.

Findings concerning scientists' perceptions of employment opportunities suggest that a majority in each group perceived a positive job market at the time they received their doctoral degrees. On the other hand, a greater percentage of non-weapons scientists than weapons scientists say that more employment opportunities were available. In addition, a greater proportion of those in group one than group two say that most of the jobs appeared to be defense-related when they graduated. On balance, the findings imply that non-weapons scientists perceived less restrictions on their employment options than weapons scientists, and that they were not as likely to see defense-related or weapons research as the primary area of possible employment.

Findings related to scientists' differential perceptions of, and relationships to, their work are notable in several important ways. First, non-weapons scientists are more likely to be interested and participate in organizations whose primary concern is the ethical and social responsibilities of scientists. Second, non-weapons scientists are more likely to agree that scientists are responsible for questioning the social and political implications of their research before engaging in it. Third, non-weapons scientists are more likely to agree that "noncooperation in military matters should be an essential moral principle for all true scientists."

Finally, it is clear that rationalization is often employed as a technique for minimizing personal conflicts concerning participation in defense-related and weapons research. While nearly two-thirds of the non-weapons scientists agree that there is a conflict between the basic goals of science and participation in weapons research, less than 40.0% of the weapons scientists agree that such a conflict exists. When asked why they participate in weapons research, many scientists often cited as reasons the a priori beneficial nature of scientific knowledge, so-called 'national security', or the fact that someone else would do weapons research if they did not. Weapons scientists also relied on theoretical distinctions between the pursuit of scientific knowledge and its subsequent applications by other non-scientists (e.g., engineers and technicians), or on differences between scientists who seek knowledge and politicians or others who make decisions about funding weapons research or deploying the end-products of such knowledge in Western Europe, underground silos, submarines, and intercontinental bombers.

Causality

Despite the theoretical emphasis in this research on the dialectical nature of relationships in the model, the question of causality arises as a fundamental concern in the interpretation of the findings – particularly those which support Hypothesis #2. **Does adherence to the values of the traditional image of science cause participation in weapons research? Or, conversely, does participation in weapons research increase belief in traditional scientific values?**

First, the design of this research is not capable of providing methodologically sound answers to the question of causality. Respondents were interviewed after they completed formal training in graduate school and had secured employment. In order to address the question of causality more fully, the research design would have to have incorporated a longitudinal study of one cohort of physical scientists. That is, in addition to the interviews conducted as part of this research, it would have been necessary to measure respondents' values prior to their employment upon completion of graduate training.

Second, even if a longitudinal study had been conducted, it is not necessarily clear that questions of causality could be answered with any degree of certainty. This is the case primarily because an understanding of how much one or more variables explain(s) variance in the dependent variable is not proof of the existence of causality. Generally speaking, sociology is neither theoretically nor methodologically capable of addressing questions of causality. Nor is it clear that sociology should be preoccupied with such questions. Concern with causality assumes an extraordinary faith in a theoretical model's ability to be isomorphic with reality. Given the reductionism implicit in any model, this condition is unlikely ever to be met with any certainty. Moreover, given this analysis' criticism of science's confusion of models and reality, it seems only appropriate to avoid committing such an error here.

Third, the statistical analyses suggest that the traditional image of science explains about 12% of the variance in the dependent variable. Speaking of causality in this situation is at best risky given the many 'unknowns' and subsequent interaction effects involved.

Questions of primacy, however, are perhaps more suited to the nature of sociological inquiry. The primacy – either temporal or theoretical (or both) – of independent variables is important to the comprehension of the theoretical implications of models as well as the interpretation of research findings. Statements about the primacy of certain variables over others are not necessarily, however, statements about causality.

It is probably the case that strong adherence to traditional scientific values increases the likelihood of participation in defense-related and weapons research, and that participation in such research may alter fundamental values. This research, however, suggests the primacy of the values of the traditional image of science for several reasons.

First, the theoretical model implies the temporal primacy of fundamental social values, which influence subsequent social action. Second, the sample was selected in order to minimize the influence of work-related experiences on their values, i.e., respondents were interviewed as soon after completing their formal training as possible. Since it is logical to suggest that the transformation of fundamental values through work-related experiences requires a sufficiently long period of time, it can be assumed that the values under investigation here are relatively intact and, on balance, represent the values of respondents at the time they graduated.

Third, and perhaps most important, is the significant degree of contradiction between adherence to traditional scientific values and respondents' perceptions of similar characteristics in their own research (as discussed earlier). These perceptions (rather than the responses to the TIS items) may be seen as representations of the influences of employment on respondents' feelings about science. Except for the possibility that the weapons scientists in the sample believe more strongly in the traditional scientific values as a way of rationalizing conflicts resulting from participation in weapons research, if stronger adherence to the TIS values is the result of participation in weapons research, one would expect a much greater degree of congruence between responses to items about the TIS values and items concerning perceptions of their own research than is evident in the data.

Support for Other Major Variables in the Model

The Social Demand for Defense-Related and Weapons Research

The assumption that there is a significant social demand for weapons research finds overwhelming support from the data. Moreover, a majority of scientists in the sample experience society's expectations of them with regard to the need for such research. Of the 73 scientists interviewed, 69 (or 94.5%) agree that there is a significant demand for weapons research in this country, and 62 (or 85.0%) agree that society depends on them for the execution of such research. The following selection from one of the interviews illustrates not only the sample's awareness of the social demand for weapons research, but also this respondent's acknowledgment of the influence the profit motive has had on scientists' ethical concerns about the directions of science, and the degree to which the social good has become irrelevant to the scientific enterprise.

What you work on a lot of times depends on what society wants to spend their money on. In this country it's primarily weapons. And if you can connect somehow to the weapons industry, you can get a lot of money, whether what you're doing is of any benefit to man or not.

[Hereafter, all quotes are from the interviewees.]

Traditional Image of Science Values

A majority of the sample agree or strongly agree with 20 of the 23 items that measure the traditional image of science (TIS) values). Respondents agree (or strongly agree) most with the following principles:

- objectivity is ideally important to science (97.3%);
- scientists can discover the 'mysteries' and 'secrets' of nature through the use of scientific methods (97.2%);
- objectivity is possible and should be pursued (94.6%); and
- scientific growth – along with economic and technological growth – leads to material progress (91.8%).

Members of the sample also agree (or strongly agree) that:

- applied science seeks knowledge in order to control the physical world (87.7%);
- the discovery of scientific 'truth(s)' is progress for humankind (86.3%);
- 'truth(s)' can be discovered through the scientific pursuit of knowledge (83.6%); and
- physical variables are the most important ones in pursuing scientific knowledge (83.5%).

Scientists' Perceptions of Their Own Scientific Research

How do physical scientists view their own research? Do they see themselves as objective? Is their work influenced by external factors or personal biases? A significantly large majority of the scientists in the sample believe that:

- they are objective in their own research (95.9%);
- their work contributes to progress in the world (94.5%);
- their research contributes to the cumulative body of scientific knowledge (90.3%);
- whatever they discover in their research will be useful somehow to our overall understanding of physical reality (90.3%);
- their research is primarily quantitative (86.3%);
- their work will contribute to our ability to control the physical world (83.6%);
- their research is helping to discover 'truths' about the physical world (83.3%); and that
- the funding for most scientific research conducted today is the result of political decisions (80.9%). In addition, a majority (61.4%) believe that they are successful in separating themselves from the phenomena they study in their research.

Comparisons of Scientists' Adherence to the Traditional Image of Science Values with Perceptions of Their Own Research

The research was designed in such a way as to identify congruences and incongruences between scientists' adherence to the traditional image of science values and perceptions of similar characteristics in their own research. (Percentages, below, refer to those agreeing with or strongly agreeing with the items mentioned).

- Respondents' views of their ability to remain objective in their own research match up with their views that objectivity is ideally important in scientific research (97.2%);
- similarly, a great majority (97.1%) of those who believe that objectivity is possible and should be pursued, believe that they are objective in their research.

However, scientists' perceptions of the political nature of funding decisions for research in the 'real world' of science provide a contradicting view of scientists' abilities to remain objective in their work:

- 81.7 percent of those who believe that objectivity is ideally important in science admit that the funding for most scientific research conducted today is the result of political decisions;
- of those who believe that objectivity is possible in research conducted today and should be pursued, 79.7% acknowledge the political influences in research funding decisions.
- Moreover, of those who believe that science should occur outside social contexts, 89.5% say that research funding decisions are politically inspired. While this is not necessarily internally inconsistent (e.g., many scientists who realize the political influences in funding decisions may wish for much less societal influence upon science), 100% of those who believe objectivity is possible in the scientific research conducted today and should be pursued admit that funding for most research is the result of political decisions.

These findings suggest significant contradictions between scientists' adherence to traditional scientific values and their assessments of what transpires in the 'real world' of science today vis-a-vis objectivity.

Objectivity

The interviews provide further insight into these contradictions between scientists' definitions of the ideal role of objectivity in science and their testimony concerning its existence in the 'real world' of science, as described below.

One of the most fascinating aspects of the interviews involves scientists' responses to statements about apparent disagreements among the respondents over the viability of the Reagan administration's space-based defense system proposals (commonly called "Star Wars"). Some scientists declared that the proposals are absolutely absurd and that anybody with a basic understanding of physics would agree. Others said that the proposals would work and that anyone who said otherwise knew nothing of the principles of basic physics. (Of the total sample, 37.7% think that such a defense system is possible and should be pursued, 11% are unsure, and 49.3% think a viable, space-based defense system is impossible).

Therefore, I began to ask later respondents about this interesting phenomenon. If scientists were truly objective and had the same facts as their colleagues, why wasn't there more agreement on the question of the viability of the "Star Wars" proposals? Did they suppose that scientists were disagreeing because of their own ideological values? And if so, what did that imply about the objectivity, value neutrality, and respectability of the scientific community? One respondent said,

I think there's a lot of crazy scientists, I really do. I'm very mad at the ones who are sort of pushing this "Star Wars" idea. It's very scary. Science just isn't completely objective and rational. It just isn't ... Scientists are some of the most stubborn, biased people you'll ever find, and that's true. The

danger is that some scientists have these strong, built-in biases, but when they find out they're wrong, they don't really admit that.

Later in the interview, I asked him what he thought would happen if most scientists refused to engage in weapons research. He liked the idea, but thought it would be difficult to get scientists to agree to do it,

... because scientists, well like I said, I think they're a very stubborn, biased class of people and, unfortunately, they don't think the same either ... So getting them to do something like that is tough.

Another scientist, when asked about the disagreement over “Star Wars”, replied,

Scientists are not science. I mean, we're people, and we're often wrong . . . We're giving opinions more than anything else.

This is a critical point. There is merit in drawing a distinction between the characteristics of individual scientists and the character of science. What the interviews illustrate, however, is a double standard that allows science to be objective when scientists are not. I pursued this line of reasoning with another respondent during one interview. He admitted that scientists are not objective and that their values influence their research, but still believed that that does not preclude the overall objectivity of science. I asked him how this could be the case. He responded that scientists just hope that the process of replicating experiments ‘cancels out’ the biases. I suggested that such a notion was not necessarily logical: that it was highly unlikely that objective research was the sum of greater and greater amounts of subjective research. He shrugged his shoulders in agreement and smiled.

Other comparisons

Scientists in the sample who believe that value-free research is ideally important are not necessarily successful in achieving value-free research themselves. Of those who agree that values should not bias research, less than half (46.2%) say they do not let values influence their own research. Similarly, only 52.3% of those who agree that value-free research is possible, believe they achieve this objective in their own research.

Comparisons between the ideal importance and realistic possibility of distinctions between subject and object in research, on the one hand, and scientists successfully separating themselves from the objects in their research, show that roughly three-fourths of the sample have values and actions that are congruent (78.3% say subject-object separation is ideal and 75.0% say it is possible). However, only 43.5% of those who agree that a subject-object distinction is ideally important – and 37.5% of those who agree that such a distinction is possible – believe that they separate themselves from the social implications of their own research.

Two quite interpretations of this finding are possible. From one perspective, if it is assumed that the inability to separate oneself from considerations of the social implications of one's research precludes the possibility of a successful delineation of subject and object, than it would appear that the scientists in the sample are believing one thing and doing another. Another interpretation, however, is that despite apparent contradictions between traditional scientific values and assessments of ‘real-world’ science, many of the scientists in the sample are concerned nonetheless with the social implications of their research.

Further comparisons also provide startling results. Of those who believe that the ‘real world’ of science occurs outside social contexts, only 28.6% say that their own research is immune from outside influences. Similarly, of those who believe that science ideally should occur outside social contexts, only 26.3% see

their own research as untouched by societal influences. These findings represent concrete contradictions between the traditional image of science values and the personal experiences of scientists in the everyday world of science in the twentieth century.

A large majority of scientists in the sample have congruent views concerning the contributions their own work makes toward discovering 'truths' about the physical world and belief in traditional values about the ways in which science discovers 'truth' or the 'mysteries' and 'secrets' of nature. Of those who believe that scientists can discover the physical world's 'mysteries' and 'secrets,' 84.3% see their own work as helping to discover 'truths' about the physical world. Of those who believe that 'truth(s)' can be discovered through the scientific pursuit of knowledge in the physical world, 86.7% say that their own research contributes to the discovery of such 'truth(s).'

Additional comparisons indicate a general congruence between responses to other items concerning the traditional image of science and scientists' perceptions of their own work, including the following.

- Of those who believe that applied science seeks to produce scientific information in order to enhance control over the physical world, 85.9% see their own research as hopefully contributing in this way.
- Of those who agree that the pursuit of knowledge is *a priori* beneficial, 95.2% believe that whatever they discover in their work will be useful somehow to our overall understanding of physical reality.
- Of those who view the discovery of scientific 'truth' as progress for humankind, 96.8% say they see their own research as contributing to such progress.
- 96.8 percent of those who believe that scientific methods are primarily quantitative see the methods they employ in their own research as such.
- Of those who say that a fundamental result of continued scientific, economic and technological growth is increased material progress, 95.5% believe that their own work is contributing to progress.
- 86.7 percent of those who believe that physical variables are of primary importance in the pursuit of scientific knowledge have never employed social, economic, political or psychological variables in their models or hypotheses, and 86.4% of those who believe nonphysical variables are of secondary importance have never used such variables in their models or hypotheses.

Conclusions: Seeing Through the Eyes of the Scientists

One thing I like about science is that it keeps me away from difficult questions ... questions that don't have answers. I like to stick with questions that have answers. Even if I can't necessarily find out the answer, I like to believe that there is an answer. And I think in social questions or anything to do with [situations] where you have more than three variables, then an answer may not be possible ... I mean, that's one of the appeals of science: that you can find an answer to a question – and it's right or wrong.
[From the interviews]

- **First, there is a demand for weapons research in the United States, and a great majority of scientists in the sample experience society's expectations of them concerning the need for such research.** Of the 73 scientists interviewed, 69 (or 94.5%) agree that there is a significant demand for weapons research in this country, and 62 (or 85.0%) agree that society depends on them for the execution of such research.
- **Second, those values which comprise the traditional image of science exist to a large extent in the value systems of the physical scientists in the sample.** Only three of the 23 items concerning

these values do not enjoy agreement by a majority in the sample. Respondents indicate that they believe most strongly in:

- the ideal importance of objectivity in scientific research,
 - the ability of science to discover the ‘mysteries’ and ‘secrets’ of nature,
 - the notion that objectivity is possible in the research conducted today and should be pursued, and
 - the belief that increased material progress is the result of continued scientific, economic, and technological growth.
- **Third, there appears to be a significant degree of contradiction between scientists' belief in the traditional image of science and their experiences in the everyday, ‘real world’ of science.** For example, in contradistinction to their concern for objectivity (97.3% agree objectivity is ideally important, 95.9% believe that they are objective in their research, 71.2% say that values should not bias research, and 66.2% believe that a delineation between subject and object is ideally important), only 39.7% agree that they do not let their personal values bias their research, and 38% are successful at separating themselves from the social implications of their research. Moreover, 84.9% admit that science as it is practiced today is influenced by society and 76.7% acknowledge that their own research is affected by social factors. These apparent contradictions support two of the premises of the investigation:
 - **adherence to the values of the traditional image of science continues despite the nature of scientific research practiced today, and**
 - **the epistemological ramifications of quantum mechanics and ‘the new physics’ do not seem to have challenged the ideological and philosophical assumptions of those scientists still influenced by the traditional image of science (e.g., 94.6% believe that objectivity is possible and should be pursued).**
 - **Fourth, there is a positive correlation between belief in the values of the traditional image of science and participation in defense-related or weapons research.** A greater percentage of weapons scientists than non-weapons scientists agree or strongly agree to 17 of the 23 TIS items. Moreover, **the percentage of scientists engaged in (or willing to engage in) such research with scale scores of four or better (out of a possible score of five) is four-and-one-half times as great as the percentage of those who will not or do not engage in military-related research.**
 - Fifth, when combined with other dominant cultural values (e.g., nationalism and patriotism, the desire for upward mobility, low self-efficacy, and a positive orientation toward both the arms race and weapons research), **these various values and perceptions may explain as much as 38% of the variation in the dependent variable.** Moreover, it appears that **values related to nationalism and patriotism contribute the most to the explanatory power of the theoretical model, and when combined with values related to the traditional image of science produce the second-most important variable vis-a-vis the model's explanatory power.**

Additional conclusions related to differences **between** the two groups of scientists in the sample can be drawn. Most important are those which relate to adherence to the values of the traditional image of science:

- Foremost among these is **the disparity between the two groups of scientists vis-a-vis the desire for science to be conducted in a social vacuum.** A majority of the weapons scientists admit to this desire, while most of the non-weapons scientists appear to acknowledge the fact that science is a social institution that cannot be separated from society.

- **Weapons scientists appear to believe that the purpose of ‘pure’ science is to seek knowledge for its own sake and that the pursuit of scientific knowledge is self-justified.** When viewed in conjunction with the above observation concerning the social nature of science, one may conclude that **weapons scientists are less likely to question science and its offspring (e.g., technological developments) than are non-weapons scientists.**
- **The traditional scientific worldview still captivates more weapons scientists today than non-weapons scientists.** The former tend to question the Cartesian delineation between mind and matter less and exhibit, instead, a greater degree of ‘scientific chauvinism’ than their non-weapons colleagues. On the other hand, non-weapons scientists appear to be more willing to acknowledge the legitimacy of other scientific disciplines and the possibility of non-scientific approaches to knowledge.
- It is clear that there is a relationship between nationalistic and patriotic values and participation in defense-related and weapons research. These values may be even more significant than the values of the traditional image of science.
- There appear to be **relationships between participation in defense-related and weapons research, on the one hand, and political ideology, party identification, religious orientation and religious commitment.** That is, in addition to their greater adherence to the values of the traditional image of science, weapons scientists can be characterized by their: greater degree of conservatism, greater identification with the Republican Party, greater identification with Protestant denominations, and more frequent church attendance.
- **Weapons scientists may be more militaristic in their approaches to social problems and other peoples than non-weapons scientists. They exhibit more positive orientations toward war as a solution to problems and toward the necessity and usefulness of weapons research, Moreover, they favor disarmament less than do non-weapons scientists.** These characteristics obviously coincide to a large extent with other dominant values in the United States (e.g., ethnocentrism) and with those tendencies toward nationalism and patriotism mentioned above.
- Finally, there may be negative relationships between political and social responsibility and participation in defense-related and weapons research. **Weapons scientists in the sample are less involved in political and public issues, less interested or willing to participate in professional organizations that deal with the social responsibilities of scientists, and less inclined to refuse to cooperate with the military in their capacity as scientists.**

Metaphors, Scientific Delusions, and Dichotomous Realities

This dissertation begins with a discussion of metaphors. It is suggested that the traditional scientific worldview is itself a metaphor that has become confused with reality; that, despite the fact that it is antiquated, it is still a powerful metaphor with profound social consequences. It is true that science is not unusual in its metaphorical grounding: all social activity is metaphorical to the extent that it employs symbols for the purpose of expression. Acknowledging this fact, however, does not invalidate the present concern for the metaphorical nature of science. On the contrary, such concern is warranted for three fundamental reasons: the tenacious power of the scientific metaphor's hegemonic sway over Western modes of perception, the inescapable vulnerability of the social and physical worlds to the misuses of scientific knowledge and its concomitant technological progeny, and the metaphor's apparent need of substantive revision.

This investigation brings attention to the metaphorical nature of science, not because it is unique, but because the traditional metaphor is contributing to basic delusions that promise grave consequences. The selection from the interviews which begins this chapter provides insight into several of these fundamental, interrelated delusions produced by the traditional scientific worldview. The first occurs when this kind of 'science' entices its young devotees into the belief that the complexity of the social world can be somehow avoided and evaded by surrounding oneself with the sacrosanctity of science.

The second delusion is that science will provide the answers. This delusion is evidence that scientific models often become confused with the reality they are intended to represent. 'Facts' come to be seen as existing independently of the social values with which they are intrinsically and dialectically related. These 'facts' become confused with scientists' perceptions of the phenomena themselves.

The third delusion is that the 'facts' represent a ubiquitous discreteness that is ever present in reality. That is, the traditional scientific worldview, still apparently unweaned from the Cartesian delineation between mind and matter, promulgates the assumption that reality is discrete and consequently susceptible to dismemberment, rather than continuous and interrelated. This is the delusion of dichotomy: that questions about the physical world can produce answers that are somehow reducible to 'right' or 'wrong'.

The traditional image of science is also a metaphor. It is only one approach to an understanding of scientific values and their influences upon specific types of social action. If this research has produced too clear or too complete an image of the differences between the two groups of scientists in the sample, then it is also guilty of the dichotomy of delusion.

What is apparent from the interviews, in fact, is that scientists are fascinatingly unique individuals. Some appeared to be more socially aware and responsible than others. Some scientists were obviously concerned about the special responsibilities of scientists in society, whereas some were visibly bothered by such considerations. Still others found discussions of the philosophical assumptions of science quite engaging, while some of their colleagues had serious difficulties thinking about philosophical issues or questioning certain ideas as assumptions.

The traditional image of science is only useful to the extent that it allows for an examination of the internal contradictions of the traditional scientific worldview and of the inherent contradictions between this worldview and the 'science' practiced in a multitude of diverse contexts today. The traditional image of science is a metaphor that invites an analysis of: 1) Merton's "imperious immediacy of interest" (i.e., the irrationality of science's rational pursuit of its primary goal – scientifically derived truth – to the exclusion of other social goals), and 2) Sorokin's concern that "empirical science" and its "objectivity" may destroy other truths and values if they continue to dominate them.

In sum, the traditional image of science is a metaphorical contribution to analytical approaches to the search for a new metaphor for science. If the "social construction of reality" thesis of Berger and Luckmann²⁷ has any validity, it would suggest that the traditional image of science is not a permanent constellation in the social heavens of science. If the crocodile or any other rapacious beast is unacceptable as a metaphor for science, scientists and society must begin the search for its successor.

The search for a new, less destructive, more holistic metaphor may begin from many different starting points. A logical first step is an investigation of the present worldview, its contradictions, and its limitations. It would seem incumbent upon society, therefore, to engage in a critical examination of its images of science and of science's contradictory social functions.

Given this society's apparent reverence for scientists and science, such a critical examination of science would have far greater validity if it were to originate with scientists and be subsequently disseminated

through society via educational forums and the media. However, judging from the interviews with scientists undertaken as a part of this doctoral research, it appears unlikely that society can rely on its young physical scientists to initiate this process. On the contrary, the interviews suggest that the majority of scientists in the sample will require significant support from society to undertake the difficult challenges related to being weaned from the traditional scientific worldview and defense-dependent employment.

Science as a Complex Social Institution

The dissertation concludes with a rather long selection from the interviews; one that is both appropriate and relevant to the overall objective of this investigation because it summarizes impressions gained through the interviews of the relationship between science as a social institution and science as politics, big business, and handmaiden to military technologies of mass destruction. Underlying this physical scientist's description of the 'real world' terrain of the scientific enterprise, i.e., of 'the way things are,' is an aquifer of hope that society will come to understand the prostitution of science through its relationship with the military, and will find a way to free science from its Faustian bargain and give it new life.

When asked why weapons research is necessary, the scientist replied,

Certain defensive and conventional weapons research could have a big payoff: they could make it so that a lot of our people don't get killed in situations where they would be before. But certain weapons have been beat to death . . .

See, that's what happens, you know. A system gets a set of proponents in the early stages, and those people tend to build an empire. People in the '50s were working on nuclear weapons – both atomic and hydrogen bombs – and they developed quite a kingdom. They get a lot of money; they get a lot of scientists working for them. And that science has matured. I mean, they're still making improvements, but it's in a mature stage. And those people don't want to lose any of their staffs, they don't want to give up the amount of money, they don't want to give up their political clout they have in Washington.

I used to work at Livermore, and that institution has a lot of money [that] goes through there. And those people know it and they like that feeling of power. They don't want to give it up. They don't want to have somebody say, "Hey, well look, we've done enough work on nuclear weapons. We don't need to spend as much now as we did in the '50s," They'll find you 50 reasons why that's wrong. That's one of the reasons I left Livermore ... It's definitely not [the ethical or right reasons to pursue science].

Just study some of the major characters: Edward Teller – he's the big guru at Livermore. And that guy is hungry for power. And power to him is the ability to create very large programs. He's one of the biggest proponents for the "Star Wars" thing. Some of his ideas I don't think are very good; but some of the concepts that are related to "Star Wars" I think are good. But I would be very mistrustful of that man. You know, he's a very dangerous type in the sense that he's very smart and a lot of what he says is very true. But his motivation is not always for the good of the country. He'll claim he's the biggest patriot in the country, but a lot of it is his institution. He's built this organization and he's a very powerful person within it. And he wants to maintain that.

When asked if he could participate in weapons research in the future, he said,

Yeah, I could see doing it in some cases ... It depends on the kind of work you're doing, too. I mean, you start doing stuff where you start talking about megadeaths and I get turned off very

quickly. And I remember where I used to work (and I tell you it wasn't the military – I was in the military, but the worst ones were the civilian contractors), and they talked about megadeaths as if you were playing a game of chess at lunch time. And that kind of atmosphere really turns me off.

But there's other cases where – for instance the “Star Wars” thing – it could be very exciting I think, and [you] could really feel like you're making a contribution to reduce the chances of a nuclear war maybe not occurring, or if it did, that the destruction of this country would be minimized. So ... I'd be very positive about that. So, it's not a black or white deal ... working on weapons systems is not a black or white [thing]: some are good, I think, and some are bad. What completely turns me off is biological warfare. I mean, that to me is clear-cut: I don't want to be connected with that at all.

You know what gets me about some of those guys is that they talk about stuff like that, yet, you know, street crime appalls them. You punch them in the nose and they see their own blood – they'll faint. I mean, I couldn't believe some of these guys. I mean, it's strictly abstract to them ... They make it very abstract.

And let me tell you the problems you try and solve in this kind of business, the defense business, are extremely challenging. You can really get excited from the technical challenge: “how do you solve this thing, how do you do this,” you know? They're very challenging in that way. And so there's a tendency to get really involved with the problem and really cop out and say, “Well, I'm not involved with how it's going to be used. The military takes the blame for all that.” You know, they're just designing an option and the military has to decide whether they want to [use it or not]. Well, that's crap. Those guys – I've been to a lot of presentations where they're selling. They're saying, “We can make this kind of system and we'd like you to buy.” They're really doing a sell job; they're not saying they've just got some option. Cause it means a lot of big bucks.

So (1) is [that] the problems are technically very interesting or challenging, and (2) there's a real tendency to make things very abstract and really disconnect what you're doing as far as how it can harm people. I mean, some of these guys are working on conventional ideas, too, and I thought, “Boy, if you ever saw what these things could do to people, you know, burn you – or different kinds of napalm or stuff like that – you'd be aghast.” But, you know, to them it's not.

At this point, he was asked how he thought science could have come so far in this direction, i.e., in being used for such purposes. He responded,

Well, I think it started in World War II. Before World War II, science was not heavily connected with the government; There was some connection, but people didn't really realize how much of a benefit weapons systems development can occur by being connected with science. Then in World War II there were a couple of real key changes. One was the development of the nuclear weapon [at] Los Alamos. The other was the development of radar. Both of those indicated to the government that science was a definite, positive contributor to [our] ability to develop new weapons. And it was at that point – during the war and after the war— that a lot of money started going towards science for its development of weapons, and [this] encouraged, you know, ICBM's and that kind of stuff. And then, you know, when you start throwing a lot of money into something like that, these organizations develop to take care of it. Then they want to enhance themselves. They have momentum and then you get what's called the “Iron Triangle”: the coupling between the defense contractors, the local politicians, and the military ... Well, I think there's a lot of truth to what [the author of *The Iron Triangle*] says.

You know, in Southern California, there's not going to be very many congressmen that say they're going to be closing down some defense plants. And one of the strategies for insuring that your weapon system will be supported in Congress is to make sure there's a little bit of it spread all around the country. The MX system is a classic case. Every congressional county, if they can do it, is going to get a little something. So no one's going to want to shut it down. So I think that's how it got started

and that's how it's continuing.

“Does this concern you?”

Oh yeah. Yeah. Definitely. Because I think it's more than just an expenditure of money. I think it's lost resources. You know, I used to go to Livermore – to be driving to work – and [think to myself], “You know, it's not just the scientific minds, but in order to do any of these scientific experiments, you've got to have the best electricians, the best plumbers.” I mean, these guys could be working on housing, they could be working on new roads, but they're out there figuring out ways to make things that are going to be used in experiments for weapons. So it's more than [the loss of] just a bunch of scientific talent. And that also is the case, I think: the loss of scientific talent is affecting our ability to compete in markets. I mean, Japanese scientists are not working on weapons. They're working on how to make VCR's and calculators and stuff like that. And we're paying [for] it.

“Were you aware that this was how science was really being used and that that's what you'd have to deal with when you got out into the ‘real world’ – when you were learning to be a scientist, when you were younger, in school?”

No. No, I don't think I became aware of that until ...

“Were you taught that science really was a good thing no matter what, and should be practiced in a context away from political influences?”

Oh yeah. Yeah. That's the fairy tale. Especially when you're in high school and even in college ... But especially in high school, you know, you get this kind of fairy tale conception about whatever science does is going to be good for the benefit of mankind, because it's generating knowledge, it's going to be useful to man. Yeah, I think that's a kind of fairy tale ... Science can be [beneficial]. It can be. It doesn't have to be that way.

The traditional image of science is the “fairy tale conception” of science. Along with historical events of the time, the traditional image of science contributed to the success of the Manhattan Project, and has continued to provide social legitimation of the relationship between science and the arms race. Many of the scientists who worked on the first atomic bomb have spent the rest of their lives attempting to share with the world some of the wisdom they learned at such cost during a very troubled time. What is apparent from the interviews, and what has immense, potential consequences for the world, is that the wisdom of these scientists is not being passed on to the generations of young scientists who follow, at a very rapid pace, in their footsteps.

I regard the employment of the atom bomb for the wholesale destruction of men, women and children as the most diabolical use of science.

Mohandas K. Gandhi²⁸

Part Two: Research and Publications in Related Areas of Inquiry, 1982-2024

Introduction

Human history can be told as a series of advances in warfare, from chariots to crossbows to nuclear-tipped missiles, and we are living through what may be the fastest advancement in weaponry ever. Ask any five veteran national security experts and you will hear about five different emerging technologies with the potential to change the world of combat. Swarms of robotic aircraft that work in unison to find and kill targets without any human oversight. Advanced cyberweapons that can immobilize armed forces and shut down electrical grids across the country. A.I.-designed bioweapons engineered to kill only those with certain genetic characteristics.

The Editorial Board, The New York Times²⁹

Dec. 9, 2025

Forty years later, the threats posed by nuclear weapons are much more complex, and much more dangerous, despite the elimination of significant numbers of them worldwide after the end of the Cold War. Nine countries now have nuclear weapons arsenals, two nations – the U.S. and Russia – control roughly 90% of the world’s nuclear weapons, and a relatively recent modernization contagion has infected all nuclear nations, resulting in a rapid revamping of the global arms race.³⁰ Today, Feb. 5, 2026, the New Start Treaty, which limited the number of deployed nuclear warheads, missiles and bombers (and deployed and non-deployed launchers) in the United States and Russia,³¹ expired, without anything to keep the two largest nuclear weapons powers from (officially) restarting the deadliest competition in the world. And as the above quote makes clear, the present threat of nuclear weapons has been joined by every kind of technology of death that scientists, technologists, engineers, and profiteers can imagine or dream up in the darkest of nightmares.

The “military-industrial complex” that President Eisenhower warned humanity about has spread globally. Within the U.S., it has spread intentionally across most geopolitical districts and thus is deeply embedded in budgets of all sizes and shapes. Super computers, biological and cyber weapons, artificial intelligence, and ‘advanced’ technologies keep Armageddon just minutes away from our lives and our consciousness, the “Doomsday Clock” of The Bulletin of Atomic Scientists lost 4 seconds on January 27, 2026, and is now set at 85 seconds to midnight,³² and the so-called ‘logic’ of deterrence theory and Mutual Assured Destruction (“MAD”) ideologies still inform the dominant ‘rational’ thinking of those who believe that nuclear weapons somehow keep us safe: from one another and from the nightmare of our combined nuclear arsenals. Plans for a U.S. ‘Golden Dome’ ‘defense’ system made up of satellites and space-based weapons is the latest malignant mutation of military logic and the misuse of technology; a defensive system that might also have offensive capabilities. The militarization of science is spreading and speeding faster than ever, and the world’s citizenry, some of us aware, many of us not, has been either asleep on duty or AWOL. Apathy, acceptance, ignorance, and denial have followed quickly upon the heels of secrecy, propaganda, misplaced patriotism, and greed.

Many of the themes and theoretical variables explored in *The Crocodile Years* still appear in the literature on nuclear weapons and weapons scientists: nationalism, patriotism, religion, political views; the pursuit of various new forms of military power; the fairytale view of science that does not question its misuse as the primary handmaiden of weapons in general and weapons of mass destruction in particular; and the belief that even more science and technology will ultimately solve the existential problems created by employing science and technology to solve non-scientific and non-technological problems in the first place.

Much has been written about the changing roles of scientists (public, political, advisory, e.g., in arms control and national nuclear policy), and their public discussions of ethics and morality in the ‘Nuclear Age’ since August 1945.³³ And it comes as no surprise that a large literature exists on arguments for and

against nuclear weapons, and the roles they play in a world still governed, happily or not, by deterrence theory. On the other hand, replicable scientific research on how scientists view science in society and in their work (weapons-related or otherwise) is much less visible in the relevant literatures of the last forty years.

Nonetheless, important explorations from a variety of disciplines (anthropology, history, journalism, philosophy, psychology, etc.), and in-depth interviews of weapons lab scientists and others have been published during the past forty years. Some of the publications highlighted below offer up portraits of scientists who engage in weapons R&D or in national weapons laboratories, and through them, we gain insight into how they think and feel about the work they do. And, of course, they also contribute significantly to a deeper understanding of how we all think about – and coexist with – the shadow of nuclear weapons and the ever-present threat of the most violent and immediate existential fate imaginable. The last three publications, in particular, also explore a time when scientists – nuclear and otherwise – found themselves contemplating and engaging in a revolutionary broadening of their social roles as scientists and public citizens.

While this discussion of more recent publications follows directly from the questions posed in *The Crocodile Years*, i.e., whether certain views of science (along with numerous other variables) correlate with scientists' participation in weapons R&D, it also expands to include: (1) how thinking about, working on, and living with nuclear weapons effects our thinking, our psychologies, our cultures, and our lives, (2) how scientists' roles have grown and changed vis-à-vis nuclear weapons discussions and policy, and (3) examples of efforts by scientists to discuss their relationships with weapons R&D and/or work to eliminate such research. All of the above shape how we continue to reimagine the role of science, scientists, scientific knowledge, and the appropriate end products of science, through complex psychological, cultural, and economic feedback loops.

Working On and Living with Nuclear Weapons

Identity and Morality; Religious and Political Values

Nuclear Rites: A Weapons Laboratory at the End of the Cold War, by Hugh Gusterson, is the first major anthropological study of weapons scientists (and anti-nuclear activists). Gusterson, who spent time with weapons scientists at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory and studied what life was like there, explores everything from individual beliefs, politics, and faiths to the cultural constructions of rules, behavior, and shared rituals. Gusterson's desire to understand weapons scientists' perspectives, values, and culture, irrespective of his own views, and the methodology he employs produce a highly objective study. Not surprisingly, religious, political, and national identity help shape the ideological perspectives of weapons scientists and the reasons they engage in weapons work: "He discovers that many of the scientists are Christians, deeply convinced of the morality of their work, and a number are liberals who opposed the Vietnam War and the Reagan-Bush agenda."³⁴

Ambiguity, Contradiction, and Paradox

Countdown: The Blinding Future of Nuclear Weapons, by Sarah Scoles, is the most recent study included here. Scoles is a science journalist and writer, and *Countdown* is a research effort that includes 83 personal interviews of workers at Los Alamos National Laboratory, Sandia National Laboratories, and Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory. Scoles' sketches of the weapons scientists she interviewed – and their work – range from the personal to the political, and from their individual perspectives to their shared workplace ethos. Some of the interviews illustrate how the scientists embrace ambiguity, contradiction, and paradox on a daily basis. For one worker,

...that entails some duality: working for the organization that maintains and betters the bombs that she agrees wholeheartedly should not exist. [This]...

*represents a paradox of the modern nuclear weapons complex: now that the bombs exist because of labs...[the labs] employ some people who detest that explosive existence and spend their days trying to ensure no more ever go off and that they eventually go away. Even nuclear workers who are in favor of the weapons also believe their existence can lead to peace. And so it is that in each nuclear weapons worker's personal narrative, they're doing the right — safe, secure, reliable — thing. The different, opposing states feel true, simultaneously.*³⁵

These themes — ambiguity, duality, paradox and “simultaneously” “opposing states” — appear in other studies and are essential components of “nuclearism” (discussed below).

The Pursuit of Knowledge vs. Solving Problems and “Science in the Service of National Security”

Another interview revealed how a college student navigated the major life choice between ‘pure’ and applied research, i.e., the basic divide between engaging in knowledge production and problem-solving:

*[The weapons labs] are focused on science in the service of national security, nuclear or otherwise. And their scientists want to do something that matters more immediately to the people of Earth than adding to basic human knowledge — noble and necessary as that may be. “The applications give me a sense of purpose, while pure, esoteric knowledge feels cold,” explains [the scientist]. “But that’s just me, and thank god many people feel differently or we’d never advance at all.”*³⁶

Whatever the reasons, the theoretical research and interviews conducted for *The Crocodile Years* did not encounter this line of reasoning. It is an important contribution to understanding how and why younger scientists might choose to engage in weapons work.

Metaphors and Euphemisms: Weapons of Mass Destruction as Life-Giving Saviors and Gods

Scoles also read Hugh Gusterson’s work and interviewed him for her book. One observation about how nuclear scientists think and speak about nuclear weapons echoes that of defense intellectuals in Carol Cohn’s research:³⁷

*...when the researchers talked about weapons, they spoke in metaphors of birth, not — as might make more sense — death and destruction...When the Trinity explosion went off as planned in 1945, for example, the code words to indicate its success were “It’s a boy.” ... Many researchers do think of the deterrent as savior, not destroyer. Nuclear weapons keep us from conflict, an attitude common within the national labs.*³⁸

Some who put their faith in deterrence theory think that nuclear weapons will keep us from war... and from using the weapons. These and many other insights speak to the ways in which weapons scientists make sense of, and rationalize, nuclear weapons and working with them. Gusterson was not alone in observing the death-as-birth (and rebirth) theme:

*Historian Spencer Weart came to a similar conclusion. “Belief in the virtues of science and technology could be so strong that even a threat of destruction might sound like a promise of peace,” he wrote in the 1988 book *Nuclear Fear*.³⁹ Weart argued that the birth analogy can extend even further ... Bombs as recreator, life giver, life keeper, savior. This line of thinking philosophically fuels the birth metaphor.*⁴⁰

All such examples of the ways in which weapons scientists think and speak about nuclear weapons — and their relationships to them — represent substantive areas of research and require separate articles. Nonetheless, most represent phenomena (and potential variables) identified in the past forty years and therefore deserve inclusion here.

Two Views of Science; Complacency and Routines

Yet another of Scoles' interviewees "...continues to see complacency with results as they are and often a lack of curiosity about underlying assumptions or alternative methods. [He] clearly subscribes a bit to the 'just asking questions' model of physics:

*"There are two cultures in science," he asserts. "One is 'take what's known now and solve problems by going around them. Just make a fix.' And then there's another which is 'solve the problem.' So I think there's a lot of going around the problem."*⁴¹

In addition, the scientist is referring, above, to the fact that lab scientists who do weapons simulations are not finding time to integrate the huge amount of existing data into their present-day simulations. "You get into a routine, and it's tough to break..."⁴² Like those in many other lines of work, weapons workers fall into routines. But with weapons, the potential danger of routines is much greater. In the section on 'nuclearism,' below, routines serve still another purpose in the presence of nuclear weapons.

The Use of Nuclear Weapons as an Indicator of the Failure of Deterrence

*I think that eventuality [the use of a nuclear bomb], which hopefully never occurs, calls into question the foundation or the existence of the mission...it means that if a nuclear bomb goes off, deterrence has failed. Its philosophy, which is the philosophy of stockpile stewardship, has been proven false. In that case, keeping the weapons because they would keep the peace didn't, in fact, keep the peace. It only kept the weapons.*⁴³

This observation can be understood, of course, as a logical, even scientific, conclusion: if a nuclear bomb is ever used as a weapon, then deterrence theory "has been proven false." However, if the use of nuclear weapons can be interpreted as a way to prove deterrence theory false – and to convince weapons scientists and others of the error of their ways – this is a bar much too high. It is a scientific experiment that requires nothing less than an existential proof. It is madness. This is where logic and empiricism fail humanity and all life on Earth.

On the other hand, this weapons scientist's comment also highlights the naked reality of deterrence theory and nuclear weapons: not unlike the moral of Hans Christian Andersen's classic fable, *The Emperor's New Clothes*, deterrence theory does not keep the peace. All it does is keep the weapons.⁴⁴

Then again, it is also possible that this scientist was just satirically displaying some of the "gallows humor" Scoles attributes to those who engage in nuclear weapons work.⁴⁵

Only some of the thinking and behavior of weapons lab workers included above is relevant to inquiries into the initial motivations of scientists to work on weapons in the first place. But all of it sheds light on how scientists working in weapons labs – our fellow human beings — make meaning from, rationalize, justify, and honor their work.

"Nuclearism," "Double Lives," "Psychic Numbing," and "Faustian Bargains"

Nuclearism and Absurdity

In *Indefensible Weapons: The Political and Psychological Case Against Nuclearism*, Robert Jay Lifton and Richard Falk introduce "nuclearism," by which they mean "psychological, political, and military dependence on nuclear weapons, the embrace of the weapons as a solution to a wide variety of human dilemmas, most ironically that of 'security'." The authors categorize nuclearism as a "disease."⁴⁶

"At the heart of the matter," Lifton begins, "are ways in which the bomb impairs our capacity to confront the bomb...Our sense is that a force capable of destroying human history must not be of it but

beyond it.” Thus, “our immediate predicament...can be summed up in a single word: “absurdity...[in fact,] we now live in a very special realm of absurdity... which has several layers...” One is “our basic structural absurdity... [i.e.,] the idea that [we] stand poised to destroy virtually all of human civilization...in the name of destroying one another.” Another is “the absurdity of our double life.” A third is “the special absurdity of the mind, our struggle...to ‘imagine the real.’” And the fourth “lies in the stance of the civilization and species threatened with annihilation — waiting for it to happen, indeed using much of its resources toward making it happen and virtually none of its resources toward preventing it.”⁴⁷

Double Lives, Doubling, and Psychic Numbing

Living with nuclear weapons means inhabiting ‘double lives;’ rationalizing our feelings of helplessness and apathy; justifying our daily lives and work; and continuing to live in fear of annihilation. Lifton notes that research by others resulted in similar observations and findings, including shared psychological themes. In one study,⁴⁸ people who underwent nuclear air-raid trainings as children in the late 1950s and early 1960s were interviewed in the 1970s about the effects these drills had on their lives, which included, “that of a double life. The people...knew that everything – themselves, their families and friends and teachers, all that they had ever touched or known or loved – could be extinguished in a moment. Yet they and everyone else seemed to go about business as usual.”

It is clear by now that these themes...have relevance for all of us. The air-raid drills are metaphors for the nuclear age. We all go through sequences of nuclear terror, numbing, and periodic return of the terror. We all experience confusion between death and massive nuclear death, the new ephemeralism and unmanageability of life, as sense of nuclear-related craziness that sometimes can extend into dangerous forms of “nuclear madness.” Above all, we all live a double life.⁴⁹

One of the major psychological studies that Lifton undertook during his career involved interviews with Japanese Hibakusha. Another involved interviews with Nazi doctors. Each study resulted in a highly acclaimed book: *Death in Life: Survivors of Hiroshima*, and *The Nazi Doctors: Medical Killing and the Psychology of Genocide*, respectively. In *The Nazi Doctors*, Lifton continued to develop his concept of ‘doubling’ and ‘double lives’:

The key to understanding how Nazi doctors came to do the work of Auschwitz is the psychological principle I call ‘doubling’: the division of the self into two functioning wholes, so that a part-self acts as an entire self. An Auschwitz doctor could, through doubling, not only kill and contribute to killing but organize silently, on behalf of that evil project, an entire self-structure (or self-process) encompassing virtually all aspects of his behavior.

Doubling, then, was the psychological vehicle for the Nazi doctor’s Faustian bargain with the diabolical environment in exchange for his contribution to the killing: he was offered various psychological and material benefits on behalf of privileged adaptation. Beyond Auschwitz was the larger Faustian temptation offered to German doctors in general: that of becoming the theorists and implementers of a cosmic scheme of racial cure by means of victimization and mass murder.”⁵⁰

Lifton identified the following ‘general characteristics’ of doubling: “...a dialectic between two selves in terms of autonomy and connection; ... [it] follows a holistic principle; ... [it] has a life-death dimension; ...[it] involves both an unconscious dimension — taking place...outside of awareness—and a significant change in moral consciousness; ... [and] a major function of doubling, as in Auschwitz, is likely to be the avoidance of guilt: the second self tends to be the one performing the “dirty work.”⁵¹

Beyond doubling, Lifton highlights additional behaviors and components of the Auschwitz self that are useful to an understanding of nuclearism. For example, by concentrating on “the technical”:

“Perhaps the single greatest key to the medical function of the Auschwitz self was the technicizing of everything. That self could divest itself from immediate ethical concerns by concentrating only on the “purely technical” or “purely professional...” [p.453]

or, within the ‘constructing meaning:’

“...the Auschwitz self takes on a larger sense of meaning. Its activities take on a logic and purpose and come to seem appropriate to the environment and its overall ethos. What that self becomes is not only acceptable but significant... Such a sense of significance is an important means of fending off feelings of guilt.” [p.458]

or, echoing Scoles’ research, the “Force of Routine:”

“The meaning derives partly from routine as such. The daily happenings and environmental rhythm at Auschwitz became (as the word’s derivation suggests) a route or path, a direction of the inner as well as the outer being.” [p.459]

The elements noted by Lifton, above, also appear in some of the other research included in this section, which suggests they are worthy of future attention and research.

Finally, a related aspect of living with nuclearism is “psychic numbing,” another term Lifton introduced into our nuclear vocabulary...one with which everyone alive today is far too familiar:

In Hiroshima, people I interviewed told me how, when the bomb fell, they were aware of people dying around them in horrible ways but that, within minutes or even seconds, they simply ceased to feel. They said such things as “I simply became insensitive to human death,” or referred to a “paralysis of the mind.” I came to call this general process psychic numbing and, in its most acute form, psychic closing-off. For survivors it was a necessary defense mechanism, since they could not have experienced full emotions in response to such scenes and remained sane...

Observing victims, I began to wonder about the numbing that must take place in those who make, test, or anticipate the use of nuclear weapons. For potential perpetrators simply cannot afford to imagine what really happens to people at the other end of the weapon.

This was true of American scientists constructing the first atomic bombs at Los Alamos in New Mexico. Responding to the call to win the race against an evil enemy to construct a decisive weapon, then after the defeat of Germany still seeing themselves as contributing to their country’s wartime military struggle... “they were frantically busy and extremely security conscious and...there was even some half-conscious closing of the mind to anything but the fact that they were trying desperately to produce a device which would end the war...” And so powerful was their scientific leadership that almost everyone else at Los Alamos “let Oppenheimer take protective custody of their emotions.”⁵²

Faustian Bargains and Doubling

Lifton’s overlapping observations and conclusions from diverse psychological studies — of nuclearism, Japanese survivors of the atomic bombs, and Nazi doctors in Auschwitz — explain how literally all of humanity – from nuclear weapons scientists, to victims of nuclear weapons, to all of us, living with the threat of nuclear weapons — experiences and suffers from nuclearism, double lives, and psychic numbing. That is, Lifton’s analyses of the most horrific kinds of violence possible, all of it by human beings preparing for war or engaging in it, produce a comprehensive framework within which contemporaneous studies can understand the nightmare of nuclearism.

Thus, although temporally and historically located within the horrors of Hiroshima and Auschwitz during World War II, Lifton’s research is universally applicable to other examinations of doubling and psychic numbing. His in-depth interviews and psychoanalytical analyses of the Nazi doctors’ “Auschwitz Self” provide insight into — and suggest variables for — future research on the rituals and psychologies connected with working on, and living with, nuclear weapons. His analysis of who these doctors became at Auschwitz contributes significantly to an understanding of how scientists living in the present age of nuclearism engage in science that results in weapons of mass destruction.

That said, it would be a grave misunderstanding to misinterpret the paragraphs above — or the inclusion and application of Lifton’s work here — as an attempt to equate weapons scientists with Nazis or Nazi doctors in any context. As Lifton makes clear, “...doubling can be understood as a pervasive process present to some degree in most if not all lives...”⁵³ Instead, the fundamental connection, here, is that Lifton’s analytical framework lends itself perfectly to an understanding of nuclearism, science in the pursuit of weapons of mass destruction, and those who labor in such work.

Essentially, Lifton’s research suggests that, in order to understand the complex beliefs, psyches, and lives of our weapons scientists, we need to understand nuclearism — the psychological reality shared by all of us. Therefore, one answer to the question posed by *The Crocodile Years*, is that how scientists view science is socially constructed by all of us, and the results effect all of us. Thus, perhaps the penultimate question becomes: how do we socially deconstruct nuclearism from within it...i.e., while we also suffer from it? The following might be a possible first clue from Lifton about where we must begin:

*One is always ethically responsible for Faustian bargains – a responsibility in no way abrogated by the fact that much doubling takes place outside of awareness.*⁵⁴

The Cold War: Context, Funding, Knowledge, Technology, and Scientists’ Roles and Responsibility

The Cold War, which lasted 45 years and nine months, fed, cradled, and nurtured the arms race between 1947 and 1991. It was also an incredibly challenging period for scientists and weapons research. Numerous publications and research explore science, scientists, weapons research, and technology during this significant period. The following four contributions, listed below chronologically, represent examples of different kinds of research within different themes during the Cold War.

Unintended Consequences: How Nuclear Weapons Production Shapes Knowledge Production and Technology

“Weapons Research and the Form of Scientific Knowledge,” by the late Ian Hacking (a philosopher of science). With regard to questions about knowledge production and unintended consequences, Hacking observes in 1986,

From time immemorial all weapons have been a product of human knowledge. Today the relationship is reciprocal. A great deal of the new knowledge being created at this moment is a product of weaponry. The transition occurred in World War II, and, in the West, was institutionalized by the new ways of funding research and development put in place in 1945-47 in the U.S.A.

Presumably this makes some difference to what we find out. Brains and equipment are dedicated to the production of knowledge and technologies useful in time of war. Our Physical Abstracts, Chemical Abstracts, Biological Abstracts, Indexus Medicus — our repositories of references to new knowledge — would look very different if we had different research priorities. That means that the content of our new knowledge is much influenced by the choice of where to deploy the best minds of our generation.⁵⁵

Thus, the more we work on weapons the more our knowledge bases will be about weapons, and, of course, the more the solutions to our future problems will be weapons. Hacking’s observation and theory about the relationship between knowledge production and weapons research would appear to have immense consequences for the fate of humankind, particularly within science, engineering, and the development of technology. It suggests, among other dynamics, the existence of an additional, inner momentum to science devoted to weapons R&D and the arms race, which would make efforts to end such science and weapons even more challenging. The only way forward, it would seem, is to conscientiously and intentionally break the cycle, by funding less – or no – weapons research, while at the same time, only funding scientific research that supports humanity, life, and the earth.

Scientific Knowledge Shaped by Context and Funding, and Research in Multiple Disciplines

Science and Technology in the Global Cold War, edited by historians Naomi Oreskes and John Krige, is part of a series entitled, *Transformations: Studies in the History of Science and Technology*, published by The MIT Press.⁵⁶

One reason for this volume’s inclusion here is that its chapters, authored by 14 historians of science and technology, focus on highly diverging fields of science and its applications. A second reason is its overarching theme: the growth of government, military, and private foundation funding for scientific disciplines during the Cold War (for military and civilian purposes), which shaped, reshaped, and distorted the directions and purposes of scientific research, resulting in differential uses of science in four countries: China, France, the Soviet Union, and the United States.

In her “Introduction,” Oreskes identifies a third reason: while many historians of science and technology “defined the debate about Cold War science” primarily within physics, this volume significantly broadens that debate to include many disciplines and research areas, just as funding during the Cold War broadened support of research in many disciplines. Oreskes also articulates a fourth reason for inclusion when she notes that many of her predecessors,

“...simply skirted the question of to what degree Cold War conditions changed the content or the character of the scientific knowledge that was produced (or not produced) ...But what is the purpose of studying the historical context of science and technology if we don’t believe that it does — or at least may — shape the content? ...This volume takes up, with vigor, the questions “What did scientists do in the Cold War?” And “Why did they do those things and not other things?”

These four reasons speak to four significant strengths of the volume. They also closely echo themes and questions explored in *The Crocodile Years*.

From Los Alamos to Vietnam: Generational Shifts, Ethical Debates, and the Roles of Scientists

Scientists at War: The Ethics of Cold War Weapons Research by Sarah Bridger (also an historian) is an award-winning examination of the complicated evolution of scientists’ ethical views about weapons research and the roles of scientists during the Cold War.⁵⁷ It traces the changing perspectives of different generations of scientists from the end of the Manhattan Project through the Vietnam War.

Bridger’s book contributes to our understanding of science and scientists in society in numerous ways. It explores and documents change within science and among scientists during an important period of cultural change in U.S. history. Second, it tells a unique story about a time when scientists spoke out publicly against specific, government-funded weapons technologies – and against participating in their research and development. In doing so, it lifts a veil of sorts, allowing the public to learn about the debates that scientists have had among themselves.

Finally (and no doubt unintentionally), *Scientists at War*, like many histories, can be viewed as a guide for those who might wish to promote similar social change in the present: in this case, with a goal of renewing and strengthening ethical debates among scientists in the present; or, perhaps, ending weapons R&D altogether. And in doing so, this history illuminates the various approaches that scientists employed.

Making Nuclear Fallout a Public Debate, and the Power of Dissident Scientists

Alison Kraft, “Dissenting Scientists in Early Cold War Britain: The ‘Fallout’ Controversy and the Origins of Pugwash, 1954-1957.”⁵⁸

This story begins in 1954, after a U.S. test in the Pacific Ocean of a 15-megaton thermonuclear bomb created widespread radioactive fallout. It ends with the success of four well-known scientists and mathematicians (Joseph Rotblat, Bertrand Russell, Linus Pauling, and Barry Commoner) – and of course many others – who took on the British Government, transformed the threat of nuclear weapons into a public issue, and along the way, began building international efforts against nuclear weapons.

Kraft states that,

... raising the fallout/testing issue clearly served their purposes...it lifted the veil of secrecy thrown over the nuclear enterprise by the British government; it provided a means to engage the public anew in matters of nuclear policy; and it provided a rallying point that brought scientists together within and beyond Britain to discuss all aspects of nuclear weapons. Scientists opposed to nuclear weapons testing at this point perhaps felt that transnational initiatives were the only viable path left open to them. They had to improvise and innovate to bring Pugwash into being. In conception, form, and aims, Pugwash was a product of the Cold War context in which it arose — a response to the distinctive set of political and societal problems occasioned by nuclear science and technology, specifically nuclear weapons and especially fallout. It was also a pragmatic response to the difficulties scientists faced in mounting effective opposition to the nuclear weapons policies of the nuclear states from within.

Kraft, an historian of science and technology, among other specialties, with a research interest in ‘science and peace’, went on to publish a book about this and related subjects in 2022: *From Dissent to Diplomacy: The Pugwash Project During the 1960s Cold War*.⁵⁹ Like Bridger, Kraft tells an important story about the growth of scientists’ roles in public debates about the uses of science in society, as well as their development as political activists, diplomats, and international actors. Scientists interested in ending weapons research and prohibiting nuclear weapons today can only benefit from the lessons learned by scientists who lived these histories.

The Scientists’ Movement, and Scientists’ Roles and Responsibility

Alice Kimball Smith, *A Peril and a Hope. The Scientists’ Movement in America: 1945-47*, and Alice Kimball Smith, “Scientists and Public Issues.”

The contributions of Sarah Bridger and Alison Kraft are not only histories of science and scientists during the Cold War, they also are examinations of the transformation of scientists’ roles and responsibilities in society during the last half of the 20th century. As it turns out, there are quite a number of historical treatments of the phenomenon that Alice Kimball Smith, in 1970, called “The Scientists’ Movement in America.”⁶⁰ In 1982, Smith returned to her exploration of this “movement” again in her article, “Scientists and Public Issues,”⁶¹ in which she states, “[t]here remain ... many questions of the utmost relevance to the place of science and scientists in our political society that are least illuminated if not finally answered by developments of 1945 and 1946, for it was a period in which practical aspects of the scientist’s dilemma were amply demonstrated.”

The “dilemma” to which she refers involves scientists inhabiting multiple, and sometimes competing, roles: “scientific competence” and “public affairs;” “natural spokesmen for the profession” and “confidential advisers to government;” and “scientists and citizens.” With regard to the effect all of this has on science, Smith asks, “[w]hat happens to the authority of science when scientists do not agree on the answer to a given question?” What happened in this journey that scientists undertook – from the 1980s to the present – is a fascinating story told by many different voices from many different perspectives.

Scientists’ and Physicians’ Organizations for the Prevention of Nuclear War, the Elimination of Nuclear Weapons, and the Peaceful Use of Science

Some of the ‘different voices’ belong to the “atomic scientists” who founded the Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists, the Federation of American Scientists, and the Pugwash Conferences on Science and World Affairs. Other voices belong to the scientists who created subsequent organizations for the prevention of nuclear war, the elimination of nuclear weapons, and/or the peaceful use of science. Some of these (along with the Russell-Einstein Manifesto and the visionary efforts of Joseph Rotblat) are highlighted briefly, below.

1945 – 1957: A Bulletin, a Federation, a Manifesto, and Pugwash

The Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists⁶² was founded immediately after the bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki by Eugene Rabinowitch (founder and first editor), along with Hans Bethe, Max Born, Albert Einstein, Robert Oppenheimer, Bertrand Russell, Leo Szilard, and other former Manhattan Project scientists.⁶³ The Bulletin’s headquarters are located in Chicago, IL. Subscriptions to the magazine, donor support, and free annual reports are available online.

The Federation of American Scientists (FAS),⁶⁴ located in Washington, D.C., was founded by “a group of scientists and engineers that emerged from those who had worked on the Manhattan Project, and those working at Oak Ridge and Los Alamos....[their] goal was to agitate for the international control of atomic energy and its devotion to peaceful uses, public promotion of science and the freedom and integrity of scientists and scientific research.”⁶⁵ A variation of their history states:

“After the devastating bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki, a group of atomic researchers, deeply concerned about the use of science for malice, created an organization committed to using science and technology to benefit humanity.”⁶⁶

Free publications are available online across a range of FAS concerns: environment, energy technology, clean energy, nuclear weapons, global risk, and state and local innovation. Donor support is welcome.

The Russell-Einstein Manifesto, Joseph Rotblat, and the Pugwash Conferences. Joseph Rotblat’s was another voice, and a powerful one. He left the Manhattan Project in late 1944 (more than half a year before V-E Day), on moral grounds; he was the only scientist to do so. Rotblat, along with Bertrand Russell and Albert Einstein were three of the eleven internationally renowned scientists who wrote and signed **the Russell-Einstein Manifesto** in 1955, which publicly spoke about the threat of nuclear weapons and also called for an international conference be convened to “assess the dangers posed to the survival of humanity by weapons of mass destruction.”⁶⁷ The manifesto was made public at a press gathering on July 9, 1955, in London.

Thus was born **the Pugwash Conferences on Science and World Affairs**, whose mission is “to bring scientific insight and reason to bear on...the catastrophic threat posed to humanity by nuclear and other weapons of mass destruction.”⁶⁸ The first international conference, entitled, “Appraisal of Dangers

from Atomic Weapons,” was held in Pugwash, Nova Scotia, Canada, in July, 1957. Twenty-two scientists from ten countries attended it. The most recent Pugwash conference (the sixty-third) was held in November, 2025, in Hiroshima, Japan.

Today, Pugwash has three offices: in Geneva, Washington, D.C., and London. There are “more than 50” national Pugwash Groups in “dozens of countries,” as well as “collaboration at a regional level.” The network’s “agenda [now encompasses] the issues of energy, environment, health, food security and international scientific cooperation that have fundamental impacts on the security and well-being of the world’s peoples.”⁶⁹

Joseph Rotblat’s Vision of Science and a Hippocratic Oath

Rotblat was the recipient of many prestigious awards during his lifetime, including the Albert Einstein Peace Prize in 1992, and the Nobel Peace Prize (which he the Pugwash Conferences shared) in 1995. In a *Science* “Editorial” in late 1999, entitled, “A Hippocratic Oath for Scientists,” he states,

The tremendous advances in pure science made during the 20th century have completely changed the relation between science and society. *Scientists can no longer claim that their work has nothing to do with the welfare of the individual or with state policies.*⁷⁰ [Emphasis belongs to this author]

Rotblat’s description of the “many scientists [who] “still cling to an ivory tower mentality founded on precepts such as ... ‘science is neutral,’ and ‘science cannot be blamed for its misapplication’...” echoes many of the young scientists interviewed for *The Crocodile Years*, who believed in the traditional image of science, i.e., the “fairy tale conception” of science.

By itself, Rotblat’s observation is sufficient evidence that this view of science was still alive and well at the close of the 20th century. His response to this view of science is one of deep concern and resoluteness:

... This amoral attitude is in my opinion actually immoral, because it eschews personal responsibility for the likely consequences of one’s actions ... Every citizen must be accountable for his or her deeds. *This applies particularly to scientists* ... It is also in their own interest, because the public holds scientists responsible for any misuse of science.” [Emphasis belongs to this author]

Rotblat then proposes several mechanisms by which an evolution in scientists’ views of science might be achieved:

- “[n]ational academies of science should explicitly include ethical issues in their terms of reference. Such issues must become an integral part of the scientists’ ethos...
- [p]rofessional organizations of scientists should work out ethical codes of conduct for their members, including monitoring of research projects for possible harm to society...
- [and it] is particularly important to ensure that new entrants into the scientific profession are made aware of their social and moral responsibilities... *One way would be to initiate a pledge for scientists, a sort of Hippocratic oath, to be taken at graduation...* [which would] stimulate young scientists to reflect on the wider consequences of their intended field of work before embarking on a career in academic or industry.”

Rotblat concludes his editorial by suggesting “the pledge initiated by the Student Pugwash Group in the United States” as one possible version of a pledge:

“I promise to work for a better world, where science and technology are used in socially responsible ways. I will not use my education for any purpose intended to harm human beings or the environment. Throughout my career, I will consider the ethical implications of my work before I take action. While the demands placed upon me may be great, I sign this declaration because I recognize that individual responsibility is the first step on the path to peace.”⁷¹

Education about the political, social, environmental, and technological effects of practicing science, ethical codes of conduct, a Hippocratic oath or pledge, and scientists taking responsibility for their actions: these are not the mad ravings of an ‘idealist.’ Just the opposite. In fact, ‘idealist’ might better describe those who believe that nuclear weapons and deterrence will make and keep us safe (‘...just a little more nuclear weaponry and technology to keep us safe from the nightmare of nuclear war escaping Pandora’s Box as well...’).

Joseph Rotblat and his coterie of brilliant colleagues come very close to proposing a Hippocratic oath in the concluding ‘Resolution’ of **the Russell-Einstein Manifesto** of 1955. Forty-four years later, it is the culminating proposal in Rotblat’s “Editorial” in *Science*. Rotblat realistically acknowledges that, “as in the medical profession, the main value of such an oath might be symbolic,” but also thinks that it would encourage those considering science-related professions “to reflect on the wider consequences,” and instill a life-long practice of ethical reflection.⁷² Each of his “Editorial” proposals deserves serious consideration by those interested in securing a world safe from nuclear weapons and war...in a world where science is used responsibly and ethically by everyone.

All of the scientists’ (and physicians’) organizations mentioned below stand on the shoulders of Joseph Rotblat and his colleagues: scientists of a unique generation, many of whom erred on the grandest, existential scale possible, who then spent the rest of their lives working for peace – and the peaceful use of science. They are as important for us to learn from as is the fairytale vision of science, where scientists believe they can pursue curiosity or ‘solve’ problems no matter the cost to society and future generations.

1961 – 2025: Scientists’ and Physicians’ Organizations for the Prevention of Nuclear War, the Elimination of Nuclear Weapons, and the Peaceful Use of Science Today

The efforts of the three organizations mentioned above, along with the those of Joseph Rotblat and so many of his colleagues over a period of decades signify a profound social change, and the world is safer as a result. Fortunately for us they are not alone. Today, numerous organizations work to prevent nuclear war, eliminate nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction worldwide, promote the use science for (only) peaceful purposes, and help educate young scientists about the ethical dimensions and responsibilities of science. A few of these organizations, founded by scientists and/or physicians, are highlighted below, in chronological order.

Physicians for Social Responsibility (PSR)⁷³ was founded in 1961 by physicians and health professionals. It’s first efforts involved “educating the public and policymakers about the egregious impacts of developing and testing nuclear weapons on human health.” One result of their study “of Strontium-90...in the human body...led to the Limited Nuclear Test Ban treaty that ended atmospheric nuclear testing.”⁷⁴ With help from PSR, International Physicians for the Prevention of Nuclear War (IPPNW) was founded in 1980, and PSR subsequently became its U.S. affiliate.

With headquarters in Washington, D.C., the organization now has 23 chapters in twenty states, and it’s scientific and medical foci have expanded to include: the pollution and health threats from coal, natural gas, gas stoves (and “blending hydrogen with methane to burn in gas stoves and furnaces in buildings”), fracking with “forever chemicals” (PFAS), and more. PSR also lobbied hard for the Start Treaty (2011) and its extension until 2026.⁷⁵ Membership and support are not limited to scientists.

The Union of Concerned Scientists (UCS)⁷⁶ was founded in 1969, “by scientists and students at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology...[when] the Vietnam War was at its height and Cleveland’s heavily polluted Cuyahoga River had caught fire. ... [It’s founders] drafted a statement calling for scientific research to be directed away from military technologies and toward solving pressing environmental and social problems.”⁷⁷ Today, UCS’ national and regional work focuses on climate, energy, transportation, food, nuclear weapons, and science and democracy, and a long list of accomplishments can be found on the its website. Reports, peer-reviewed papers, and a variety of resources are available online. The UCS national headquarters are in Cambridge, MA; regional offices are located in Washington, DC, Berkeley, CA, and Chicago, IL. Membership and donor support are welcomed.

Student Pugwash USA⁷⁸ was created in 1979. Its mission is essentially the same as the initial Pugwash, but with a focus on students and young professionals and building a network. As noted in the description of Pugwash Conferences above, all student members take a pledge.⁷⁹ In 1983, chapters were added to the network: they can be structured as “established,” “informal,” “startups,” or “virtual” chapters.⁸⁰ The Student Pugwash USA and The Rotblat Society are located with the Washington, DC office of the Pugwash Conferences on Science and World Affairs.

International Physicians for the Prevention of Nuclear War (IPPNW)⁸¹ was founded in 1980. Four years later, in October, 1984, it won **The UNESCO Prize for Peace Education**, and the following year it won the **1985 Nobel Peace Prize** “for spreading authoritative information and by creating awareness of the catastrophic consequences of nuclear war.”⁸² Located in U.S. in Malden, MA, IPPNW...

“is a non-partisan federation of national medical groups in 56 countries, representing tens of thousands of doctors, medical students, other health workers, and concerned citizens who share a common goal of creating a more peaceful and secure world freed from the threat of nuclear annihilation and armed violence.

IPPNW “launched” the **International Campaign to Abolish Nuclear Weapons (ICAN)** in 2007.⁸³

The International Campaign to Abolish Nuclear Weapons (ICAN) is “a coalition of non-governmental organizations in one hundred countries promoting adherence to and implementation of the **U.N. Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons**.”⁸⁴ Ten years later, on July 7, 2017, the U.N. adopted the treaty. Five months after that, on December 10, ICAN received the **2017 Nobel Peace Prize** “for its work to draw attention to the catastrophic humanitarian consequences of any use of nuclear weapons and for its ground-braking efforts to achieve a treaty-based prohibition of such weapons.”⁸⁵ On January 22, 2021, the treaty went into effect. ICAN’s headquarters are located in Geneva, Switzerland.

The Rotblat Society.⁸⁶ In 2020, Student Pugwash USA formed The Rotblat Society, in order to invite in “a general public of ‘post-educational’ members,”⁸⁷ i.e., “to promote [and extend their] primary mission to...all people who want to learn more about science or its ramifications to society, and to professionals at any point in their career.”⁸⁸ The Student Pugwash USA and The Rotblat Society are located with the Washington, DC office of the Pugwash Conferences on Science and World Affairs.

The Physicists Coalition For Nuclear Threat Reduction⁸⁹ was founded at Princeton University’s Program on Science and Global Security in 2019...and began operation in 2020...⁹⁰ The Coalition “works to reduce the threats from nuclear weapons by mobilizing advocacy with the physical sciences communities in the United States and internationally.”⁹¹ It offers colloquia in order to “build a national network of physicist-advocates,” engage in advocacy with the public and government, and work to “strengthen the participation of graduate students, postdocs, and early-career physicists and engineers in

advancing nuclear weapons threat reduction.”⁹² Anyone interested in the work of the Physicists Coalition For Nuclear Threat Reduction may join, receive their monthly newsletter and updates on their work.

The Science4Peace Forum was founded in late March, 2022, on the belief that “science and scientific cooperation can serve as a promoter for peace.”⁹³ Its members include “scientists, employees and associates working in particle physics at DESY (Hamburg)⁹⁴, CERN (Geneva)⁹⁵, [and] different universities and research laboratories,” and others. It began, “as a reaction to restrictions on scientific cooperation because of the war to Ukraine, by “a group of people at DESY... and was preceded by several peace-related groups at DESY an CERN.”⁹⁶

The Science4Peace Forum hosts regular seminars, public events, discussion, a publications section (which include articles by scientists and S4P members), and links to numerous initiatives, statements, information, news, appeals and funds related to its mission. Recent working discussions have focused: on ending support for, and research on, nuclear weapons; and ending the wars in Ukraine and Gaza, and supporting victims of these wars.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The social institution of science is powerful, immense, complex, and constantly changing. Simple generalizations about what it is and estimations of where it will lead us in the future are unwise and unhelpful. However, continuing to repeat the mistakes of the past is not an option if humankind wishes to survive itself. Neither is burying one’s head in the sand and hoping for the best.

The increasing danger of nuclear weapons (in fact, all weapons of mass destruction) – and the threat of someone or some country using them – is extraordinarily high. Just 85 seconds away on the Doomsday Clock. On the other hand, examples of progress and painful lessons learned from 1945 to the present invite us to build on the important work of individuals, institutions, and organizations to date. This way forward lies science’s best hope.

The most recent example of the individual and collective courage of scientists, is *Quantum Scientists for Disarmament: a Manifesto*, posted online on January 13, 2026. Its main goals are:

- *To express, as a unified collective, our rejection of the use of our research for military purposes,*
- *To open a debated in our community about the ethical implications of quantum research for military purposes,*
- *To create a forum where concerned scientists can share their opinions and join forces in support of demilitarized research, and*
- *To advocate for the establishment of a public database listing all research projects at public universities funded by military or defense agencies.*⁹⁷

This new initiative, which grew out of conversations among scientists in a discussion session at a recent workshop, is a sign of increasing ethical concern in scientific communities about the ways in which their work is funded and the end products of their research, i.e., the extent to which they may be participating in the military-industrial complex of today. Such conversations are increasing among scientists, especially those who work in fields most likely to be of interest – in the age of nuclearism – to those in the business of weapons production and war.

The research undertaken for *The Crocodile Years* (summarized in Part I, above) suggests that how science is understood and envisioned can influence how it is practiced. Moreover, some of the examples of research and published work done since then (highlighted in Part II, above) make it clear that: (a) some

still embrace versions of this vision of science, and (b) the militarization of science and the R&D related to technologies of mass destruction today are orders of magnitude greater than in Oppenheimer's day.

The studies included in Part II examine the nature of working on, and living with, nuclear weapons. They suggest we investigate identity, morality, religious and political values; science that is limited to either solving problems or in the service of national security; views of weapons as life-giving saviors and gods; complacency and routines; financial incentives, and the problem with discovering the failure of deterrence only after the use of nuclear weapons. They illustrate how scientific knowledge is shaped differentially by funding and disciplinary contexts, and how nuclear weapons production shapes the production of knowledge and technology. They also remind us that social roles – including the roles of scientists – are socially defined, and that they are constantly being redefined and reconstructed.

As difficult as it might be to read about 'nuclearism,' 'psychic numbing,' 'doubling,' 'Faustian bargains,' and Nazi doctors, Lifton's research, theories, and insights are probably the most relevant to those attempting to accurately comprehend our current predicament: they are, perhaps, the most essential to an understanding of the world we now inhabit and the lives we now live. In science as in society, the way a problem is defined determines (and limits) the solution(s) chosen. Lifton's understanding of the 'absurdity' of lives lived in the age of nuclearism is an immense gift, and this knowledge can help us permanently escape it.

In conclusion, these efforts shed light on the future theories, constructs, and variables necessary to test, and later design, scientific, technological and social solutions to help us move beyond research on, and development of, weapons and technologies of mass destruction. Stated differently: given that violence only reproduces itself (rather than solves – or resolves – itself), in future, *all* of our solutions to problems (whether social, economic, environmental, scientific, or technological) must be *creative*, not *destructive*; they must help us move beyond violence against all life (human and non-human) and the world we share as our home.

Individually, each scientist has the same rights and political power as every other citizen. Collectively, scientists have the power to become the 'Achilles' heel' of the military-industrial complex.

Many conscientious objectors to war understand Gandhi's theory of power, i.e., without the consent of the governed, a leader – or a government – has no power. Wars cannot be fought without weapons.

What if they gave a war and nobody came...⁹⁸

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Endnotes

Part I

- ¹ Summaries of major portions of the dissertation (e.g., on the sociologies of knowledge and science) are not included here, due to space considerations.
- ² Maris Cakars, (ed.), *There is No Way to Peace, Peace is the Way. A Book of Quotations. The 1983 WRL Peace Calendar*. NY: War Resisters League. 1983.
- ³ Robert Jungk, *Brighter Than A Thousand Suns. A Personal History of the Atomic Scientists*. Translated by James Cleugh. NY: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich. 1958.
- ⁴ As it turns out, crocodiles can turn their heads from side to side. In fact, this ability is a necessary prerequisite for the crocodile's preferred mode of attack: a sideways lunge at its prey. At best, Kapitza's remarks can only be attributed to folk-lore and myth.
- ⁵ Jon Else, *The Day After Trinity*. 1980. A film, directed and produced by Jon Else, in association with KTEH TV (Channel 54), San Jose, CA. First broadcast on PBS on April 28, 1981.
- ⁶ Jon Else, *Ibid*.
- ⁷ Alice Kimball Smith, *A Peril and a Hope. The Scientists' Movement in America: 1945-47*. Cambridge: The M.I.T. Press. 1970.
- ⁸ Smith, *Op. cit.*, p.5, 1970. Smith suggests that this argument came late in the history of the project: "[p]erhaps a few scientists thought quite early that atomic weapons might provide the *reductio ad absurdum* for major wars, but for most this was a later rationalization."
- ⁹ Else, *Op. cit.*, 1980.
- ¹⁰ Joseph Rotblat was the only scientist to leave the Manhattan Project, and did so, for moral considerations, in late 1944, more than half a year before V-E Day.
- ¹¹ The theoretical components of the dissertation benefit greatly from the sociology of knowledge and the sociology of science. Readers interested in these bodies of knowledge are encouraged to read the complete dissertation.
- ¹² Jerome R. Ravetz, *Scientific Knowledge and its Social Problems*. Oxford: Clarendon Press. 1971. This is Ravetz's definition of ideology.
- ¹³ Fritjof Capra, *The Tao of Physics. An Exploration of the Parallels Between Modern Physics and Eastern Mysticism*. New York: Bantam Books. 1975.
- ¹⁴ Alfred North Whitehead, *Science and the Modern World*. Lowell Lectures, 1925. New York: The Free Press. 1967, p.48-51, 58-9. (1925). In his study of the evolution and philosophy of science, Whitehead provides an insightful characterization of the traditional image of science. He argues that, at the heart of traditional scientific thought, there is a fundamental assumption concerning the "conception which is supposed to express the most concrete aspect of nature ... [i.e., matter, which] is anything which has [the] property of simple location." That is, scientists of the 17th century accepted the notion that the world was, "a succession of instantaneous configurations of matter...". Whitehead observes:

We cannot wonder that science rested content with this assumption as to the fundamental elements of nature. The great forces of nature, such as gravitation, were entirely determined by the configurations of masses. Thus, the configurations determined their own changes, so that the circle of scientific thought was completely closed. This is the famous mechanistic theory of nature, which has reigned supreme ever since the seventeenth century. It is the orthodox creed of physical science. Furthermore, the creed justified itself by the pragmatic test. It worked. Physicists took no more interest in philosophy. (p.50) [Emphasis is the author's.]

The assumptions of the "mechanistic theory of nature" were maintained and promulgated by the dominant philosophical directions of the 18th century:

Sometimes it happens that the service rendered by philosophy is entirely obscured by the astonishing success of a scheme of abstractions in expressing the dominant interests of an epoch. This is exactly what happened during the eighteenth century. Le philosophes were not philosophers. They were men of genius, clear-headed and acute, who applied the seventeenth century group of

scientific abstractions to the ana-lysis of the unbounded universe. Their triumph, in respect to the circle of ideas mainly interesting to their contemporaries, was overwhelming. Whatever did not fit into their scheme was ignored, derided, dis-believed. (p.59) [Emphasis is the author's.]

The assumption of “simple location”, however, is a product of the Cartesian delineation between mind and matter. As Whitehead argues, this assumption contributes to “The Achilles heel of the whole system” of scientific thought:

*This idea [of simple location] is the very foundation of the seventeenth century scheme of nature. Apart from it, the scheme is incapable of expression. I shall argue that among the primary elements of nature as apprehended in our immediate experience, there is no element whatever which possesses this character of simple location. It does not follow, however, that the science of the seventeenth century was simply wrong. I hold that by a process of constructive abstraction we can arrive at abstractions which are the simply-located bits of material, and at other abstractions which are the minds included in the scientific scheme. Accordingly, the real error is an example of what I have termed: *The Fallacy of Misplaced Concreteness.** (p.58) [Emphasis is the author's.]

Whitehead's argument concerning the “Fallacy of Misplaced Concreteness” is a reminder that science is the art of creating models of “reality” through abstraction. Whitehead correctly points out that the error of the mechanistic view of reality of the 17th century was the confusing of the model with the “reality” it was intended to represent. That is, it was “the accidental error of mistaking the abstract for the concrete.”

- ¹⁵ See Bernal (1967), Coser (1965), Crowther (1967), Ravetz (1971) and Heims (1980) for detailed accounts of the establishment of the Royal Society. Heims (p. 360) discusses the social function of “the myth of value neutrality” as follows:

The first pillar [of the ethos of science], the myth of value neutrality, has had an important social function for the growth of modern science since it was first institutionalized by the establishment of the Royal Society in England in the seventeenth century: scientists needed and wanted the support of the theological and political powers, and this support could most easily be obtained if science in no way challenged religious political authority...The society conveniently outlawed the subjects of theology and political from its meetings, emphasizing useful practical knowledge, and was granted a royal charter by Charles II.

Thus, as the period of “academic” science progressed, what was once the product of political expediency (i.e., value neutrality) became embodied in scientific activity and theory as both fundamental principle and goal.

¹⁶ Ravetz, Op. cit., p.40, 1971.

¹⁷ Heims, Op. cit., 1980.

¹⁸ Alvin Gouldner, *The Coming Crisis of Western Sociology*. New York: Basic Books. 1970.

¹⁹ Gouldner, *Ibid.*, pp.491-2, 1970, describes this principle more fully:

So long as this was a conception of the physical ... sciences, it was an ideology (1) behind which all “humanity” might unite in a common effort to subdue a “nature” that was implicitly regarded as external to man, and (2) with which to promote technologies that could transform the universe into the usable resource of mankind as a whole. Such a conception of science was ... a tacitly parochial conception of the relationship of the human species to others; it postulated humanity's lordship over the rest of the universe and its right to use the entire universe for its own benefit, a right tempered only by the species' expedient concern for its own long-range welfare. If such a view of science was an expression of the unthinking ethnocentrism of an expanding animal species,

it was also an historical summit of this species' idealism; limitations were ignored in the flush of an optimistic sense that the newly realized universalism of science constituted an advance over the narrower and more ancient parochialisms – and so it was.

²⁰ Heims, Op. cit., p.360, 1980.

²¹ Capra, Op. cit., p.31, 1982.

²² Capra, Ibid., 1982.

²³ The geographical nature of the sample creates few, if any, limitations on the potential to infer to the larger Population or to the universe, since there are no theoretical arguments that geographic location within the United States has any bearing on the relationships in the model. However, the ability to infer the findings beyond the sample is limited by the fact that the sample is not random and is self-selected to some extent.

²⁴In order to maximize the influence of anticipatory socialization (and minimize that of developmental socialization), the universe from which the sample was derived included those physical scientists who had recently completed their formal socialization in institutions of higher learning and are currently employed in research or professional capacities related to their formal training. That is, the universe consists of all those who received doctorates in physics, its subdisciplines, or related disciplines from one of the appropriate doctoral programs throughout the United States in 1983. Graduate students in these disciplines appear to be among those most likely to have the necessary skills for weapons research.

However, the findings need to be interpreted with caution for several reasons. First, the sample size is relatively small (N=73), which has the effect of rendering some of the statistics less meaningful than they would otherwise be with a larger sample. Second, this research is exploratory in nature, therefore, it is proper to place an emphasis on the descriptive findings and avoid over-reliance on statistics that require numerous assumptions that can be met by the data only some of the time.

²⁵ This respondent was a bit insecure due to the fact that he was not a citizen of the United States, he was working at NASA Ames, and he was in unfamiliar surroundings (this interview took place in my parents' home).

²⁶ It must also be assumed that the sum of positive responses to items on participation in defense-related or weapons research represents a conservative figure in relation to the total number of respondents in the sample. This assumption compensates for hesitancy on the part of some sample members to admit either to themselves or to the interviewer that they engage in this type of research.

²⁷ Berger, Peter L., and Thomas Luckman, *The Social Construction of Reality. A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge*. Garden City: Doubleday. 1966.

²⁸ Mohandas K. Gandhi, *Non-Violence in Peace and War. Volume 2*. Ahmedabad, India: Navajivan Publishing House. 1948.

Part II

²⁹ The Editorial Board, The New York Times, “Targeted Bioweapons. Drones That Kill on Their Own. This is the Future of War.” <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2025/12/09/opinion/editorials/us-china-military-ai-tech.html>.

³⁰ “Nuclear risks grow as new arms race looms – new SIPRI Yearbook out now.” June 16, 2025. <https://www.sipri.org/media/newsletter/2025-june-0>. Accessed on Nov. 25, 2025.

³¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/New_START.

³² <https://thebulletin.org/2026/01/press-release-it-is-85-seconds-to-midnight/#post-heading> .

³³ Examples include: Alice Kimball Smith, “Scientists and Public Issues,” *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*, 38:10, 38-45, 1982. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00963402.1982.11455822> ; and Sarah Bridger’s, *Scientists at War: The Ethics of Cold War Weapons Research*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press. 2015.

³⁴ Nuclear Rites: A Weapons Laboratory at the End of the Cold War. Hugh Gusterson. “About the Book.” University of California Press. 1996. <https://www.ucpress.edu/books/nuclear-rites/paper> .

³⁵ Sarah Scoles, Op.cit., p.16.

³⁶ Scoles, Ibid., p.19.

³⁷ Carol Cohn, “Sex and Death in the Rational World of Defense Intellectuals,” *Signs*, Pp. 687-718, No.4, Vol.12, 1987.

³⁸ Scoles, Ibid. Of course, the weapons don’t “keep us from conflict:” conflict is ubiquitous and part of human existence. So the conflict(s) already exist(s).

³⁹ Spencer R. Weart, *Nuclear Fear: A History of Images*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1988, cited in

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- Scoles, *Ibid.*, p.200.
- ⁴⁰ Scoles, *Ibid.*
- ⁴¹ Scoles, *Ibid.*, p. 221.
- ⁴² Scoles, *Ibid.*, p.223.
- ⁴³ Sarah Scoles, *Countdown: The Blinding Future of Nuclear Weapons*. New York: Bold Type Books. P.224. 2024.
- ⁴³ Scoles, *Ibid.*, p.224.
- ⁴⁴ Or, more generally and fundamentally, there is no peace with weapons or war ... and there never will be. Peace isn't the simple interlude between wars or the absence of all forms of violence. Peace isn't a negative. It is, instead, the presence of many other qualities, including justice.
- ⁴⁵ Scoles, *Ibid.*, p.18.
- ⁴⁶ Robert Jay Lifton and Richard Falk, *Indefensible Weapons: The Political and Psychological Case Against Nuclearism*. New York: Basic Books, Inc Publishers. P.ix, 1982.
- ⁴⁷ Lifton and Falk, *Ibid.*, pp.3-7.
- ⁴⁸ Michael J. Carey, "Psychological Fallout," *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*. Pp. 20-24, Vol. 38, Jan. 1982.
- ⁴⁹ Lifton and Falk, *Ibid.*, pp.49-52.
- ⁵⁰ Robert Jay Lifton, *The Nazi Doctors: Medical Killing and the Psychology of Genocide*. New York: Basic Books. P.418, 1986, 2000.
- ⁵¹ Lifton, *Ibid.*, p.419.
- ⁵² Lifton and Falk, *Op.Cit.*, pp.101-02.
- ⁵³ Lifton, *Ibid.*, p.464.
- ⁵⁴ Lifton, *Ibid.*, p.418.
- ⁵⁵ Ian Hacking, *Weapons Research and the Form of Scientific Knowledge*. *Canadian Journal of Philosophy, Supplementary Volume, vol. 12: Nuclear Weapons, Deterrence, and Disarmament*, pp. 237-260, 1986. Published online by Cambridge University Press. January 1, 2020.
Note: This author was unable to gain access to the article, thus the quote from an "Extract" by Ian Hacking at: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/canadian-journal-of-philosophy-supplementary-volume/article/abs/weapons-research-and-the-form-of-scientific-knowledge/8C075F21EA063732AA99E302516489DC>.
- ⁵⁶ Naomi Oreskes, John Krige (Eds.), *Science and Technology in the Global Cold War*. Series: Transformations: Studies in the History of Science and Technology. Publisher: The MIT Press. Published: 31 October 2014. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/9780262027953.001.0001>. ISBN electronic: 9780262326100.
- ⁵⁷ Sarah Bridger, *Scientists at War: The Ethics of Cold War Weapons Research*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard. April 2015. It won two awards: The Society for U.S. Intellectual History's 2016 annual book award and, as a dissertation, the 2012 Allan Nevins Prize of the Society of American Historian.
- ⁵⁸ Alison Kraft, "Dissenting Scientists in Early Cold War Britain: The "Fallout" Controversy and the Origins of Pugwash, 1954-1957." In *Journal of Cold War Studies*. Published April 1, 2018. V. 20 (1): 58-100. Publisher: Journals Gateway.
- ⁵⁹ SpringerBriefs in History of Science and Technology. Kraft, Alison, *From Dissent to Diplomacy: The Pugwash Project During the 1960s Cold War*. Springer Cham. 2022. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-031-12135-7>.
- ⁶⁰ Smith, *Op. cit.*, 1970.
- ⁶¹ Smith, Alice Kimball, "Scientists and Public Issues," *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*, vol. 38, issue 10, 1982. Published online: Sep. 15, 2015. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00963402.1982.11455822> .
- ⁶² <https://thebulletin.org> .
- ⁶³ 'Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists' entry in Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bulletin_of_the_Atomic_Scientists. Visited on Jan 27, 2026.
- ⁶⁴ <https://fas.org> .
- ⁶⁵ <https://fas.org/history/> .
- ⁶⁶ <https://fas.org/about-fas/> .
- ⁶⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Russell-Einstein_Manifesto.
- ⁶⁸ <https://pugwash.org/about-pugwash/>.
- ⁶⁹ <https://pugwash.org/pugwash-community/>.
- ⁷⁰ Joseph Rotblat, "A Hippocratic Oath for Scientists," an "Editorial" in *Science*, vol. 286, no. 5444, p. 1475. Nov. 19, 1999. <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.286.5444.1475>.
- ⁷¹ Rotblat, *Ibid.*

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- ⁷² Rotblat, Ibid.
- ⁷³ <https://psr.org> .
- ⁷⁴ <https://psr.org/about/history/> .
- ⁷⁵ <https://psr.org/about/history/> .
- ⁷⁶ <https://www.ucs.org> .
- ⁷⁷ <https://www.ucs.org/about/history> .
- ⁷⁸ <https://www.studentpugwash.org> .
- ⁷⁹ <https://www.studentpugwash.org/pugwash-pledge-sample-text>.
- ⁸⁰ <https://www.studentpugwash.org/chapters>.
- ⁸¹ <https://www.ippnw.org> .
- ⁸² <https://www.nobelpeaceprize.org/laureates/1985>.
- ⁸³ <https://www.ippnw.org/about#mission> .
- ⁸⁴ <https://www.icanw.org>.
- ⁸⁵ <https://www.nobelpeaceprize.org/laureates/2017> .
- ⁸⁶ <https://www.spusa.org/rotblat-society> .
- ⁸⁷ <https://www.studentpugwash.org/rotblat-society>.
- ⁸⁸ <https://www.studentpugwash.org/rotblat-society>.
- ⁸⁹ <https://physicistscoalition.org>.
- ⁹⁰ <https://physicistscoalition.org/leadership-and-team/>.
- ⁹¹ <https://physicistscoalition.org/mission-statement/>.
- ⁹² <https://physicistscoalition.org>.
- ⁹³ <https://science4peace.com>.
- ⁹⁴ DESY: Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (German electron synchrotron), is a particle accelerator, is located in Hamburg and Zeuthen, Germany. <https://desy.de> or https://desy.de/index_eng.html.
- ⁹⁵ CERN: The European Organization for Nuclear Research, is the home of multiple particle accelerators, including the world's largest, the Large Hadron Collider. CERN is located on the Franco-Swiss border near Geneva, Switzerland. <https://home.cern/science/accelerators/large-hadron-collider>.
- ⁹⁶ <https://science4peace.com/about-us.html>.
- ⁹⁷ https://disarmquantum.com/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/Manifesto-quantum_scientists.pdf . Also available on arXiv: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2601.14282> .
- ⁹⁸ A copy of this poster is in the Library of Congress. Created in 1969, it was ubiquitous throughout the U.S. during the Vietnam War. It speaks to the power of the individual (and one's conscience) with respect to social change, and to the power of conscientious objection to war.

